

UNIVERSITY OF SIEGEN

Visible Light Positioning Using Arrays of
Time-of-Flight Pixels

a master's thesis authored by

Zhibin Liu

and supervised by

Dr.-Ing. Miguel Heredia Conde

Prof.-Ing. Nobby Stevens

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Abstract

With the development of the economy and modern technology, location information has become more and more critical in recent years. Global Positioning System (GPS) has become an essential tool for outdoor positioning, navigation, and path planning, but GPS cannot be applied to indoor scenarios due to the blockage by buildings. In the context of “Industry 4.0” , the traditional industrial model is replaced by intelligent manufacturing. For example, a smart warehouse facilitates the optimization of transport routes, the full utilization of storage space, and advance planning. The high efficiency and low scrap rate of smart production lines also attract more industries to transform. Location information plays a crucial role in information exchange. Indoor positioning based on Bluetooth, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), and other technologies is difficult to be widely used because of high cost, low positioning accuracy, and potential interference. As traditional incandescent lamps are gradually replaced by Light-Emitting Diodes (LEDs), LED-based Visible Light Positioning (VLP) has become an increasingly attractive alternative for indoor positioning. Additionally, NIR emitters of high-speed LiFi links can also be exploited for NIR Optical Wireless Positioning (OWP). So far, receivers in VLP systems can be divided into two categories: one is the photodiode (PD), and the other are the Image Sensors (ISs), which sample in the temporal and spatial domains, respectively.

With the development of digital imaging technology, cameras have been studied as the sensor of choice in a wide range of applications. With the application of Time-of-Flight (ToF) cameras in a wide variety of products, ToF cameras are also becoming widely spread. ToF camera modules generate an illumination control signal, which is used to drive a fast light source, so that it emits high-frequency amplitude-modulated

near-infrared light. After the light is scattered by the scene objects, the receiver calculates the depth information by the phase shift or time difference between transmitted and received signals.

ToF cameras can provide both temporal and spatial resolution in a single sensor, thus posing a superior alternative to either PD or IS. The use of ToF cameras has attracted increasing attention in VLP systems. Provided that external LEDs or Vertical Cavity Surface Emitting Lasers (VCSELs) are used as signal sources, so the illumination control system of ToF cameras is no longer required. We have demonstrated by a mathematical model that the intensity pattern of LED in the amplitude image approximately follows a Gaussian distribution. Therefore, the coordinates of the LED center point can be obtained using Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) or Expectation-Maximization (EM) estimation for the amplitude image, and thus the distance information of the corresponding point can be found from the depth image.

We have successfully simulated indoor positioning using the Angle Of Arrival (AOA) algorithm leveraging knowledge of the lens normals of the ToF camera and the Time Difference Of Arrival (TDOA) algorithm based on the hybrid Chan/Taylor method. We have proved through numerous experiments that the accurate light-based positioning is feasible from measurements of a ToF camera.

Keywords: ToF camera. Visible Light Positioning. Time Difference of Arrival. Angle of Arrival. Optical Wireless Positioning.

Zusammenfassung

Mit der Entwicklung der Wirtschaft und der modernen Technologie sind Standortinformationen in den letzten Jahren immer wichtiger geworden. GPS ist zu einem unverzichtbaren Tool für Positionierung, Navigation und Wegplanung geworden, aber GPS kann aufgrund der Blockierung durch Wände nicht in Innenräumen eingesetzt werden. Im Kontext von „Industrie 4.0“ wird das traditionelle Industriemodell durch eine intelligente Fertigung ersetzt. Ein intelligentes Lager ermöglicht beispielsweise die Optimierung der Transportwege, die vollständige Nutzung des Lagerraums und die Vorausplanung. Auch die hohe Effizienz und die geringe Ausschussquote intelligenter Produktionslinien locken immer mehr Industrien zur Umstellung. Standortinformationen spielen bei der Informationsinteraktion eine entscheidende Rolle. Die Positionierung in Innenräumen basierend auf Bluetooth, RFID und anderen Technologien ist aufgrund der hohen Kosten, der geringen Positionierungsgenauigkeit und der potenziellen Interferenzen nur schwer zu verbreiten. Da die traditionellen Glühlampen allmählich durch LED-Lampen ersetzt werden, sind LED-basierte VLP-Systeme eine zunehmende Alternative für die Positionierung in Innenräumen geworden. Darüber hinaus können die NIR-Sender von Hochgeschwindigkeits-LiFi-Verbindungen auch für die OWP genutzt werden. Bisher können die Empfänger in VLP-Systemen in zwei Kategorien eingeteilt werden: die eine ist der PD, die andere sind die ISs, die jeweils im zeitlichen und räumlichen Bereich abtasten.

Mit der Entwicklung der digitalen Bildgebungstechnologie wurden Kameras als Sensor der Wahl für eine Vielzahl von Anwendungen untersucht. Mit der Anwendung von ToF-Kameras in vielfältigen Produkten werden auch ToF-Kameras immer weiter verbreitet. ToF-Kamera-Module erzeugen ein Beleuchtungssteuersignal, das zur Ansteuerung

einer schnellen Lichtquelle verwendet wird, so dass diese hochfrequentes, amplitudenmoduliertes Nahinfrarotlicht aussendet. Nachdem das Licht von den Objekten der Szene gestreut wurde, berechnet der Empfänger die Tiefeninformation anhand der Phasenverschiebung oder der Zeitdifferenz zwischen gesendeten und empfangenen Signalen.

ToF-Kameras können sowohl zeitliche als auch räumliche Auflösung in einem einzigen Sensor bieten und stellen damit eine bessere Alternative als PD oder IS dar. Die Verwendung von ToF-Kameras hat in VLP-Systemen zunehmende Aufmerksamkeit erregt. Sofern externe LEDs oder VCSELs als Signalquellen verwendet werden, ist die Beleuchtungskontrolle von ToF-Kameras nicht mehr notwendig. Wir haben mit einem mathematischen Modell gezeigt, dass das Intensitätsmuster der LED im Amplitudenbild annähernd einer Gaußschen Verteilung folgt. Deshalb kann die MLE- oder EM-Schätzung des Amplitudenbildes die Koordinaten des Mittelpunkts der LED ermitteln, und somit kann die Entfernungsinformation des entsprechenden Punktes im Tiefenbild gefunden werden.

Wir haben die Positionierung in Innenräumen mit einem auf der Kenntnis der Linnennormalen der ToF-Kamera basierenden AOA-Algorithmus und einem auf der hybriden Chan/Taylor-Methode basierenden TDOA-Algorithmus erfolgreich simuliert. Wir haben durch zahlreiche Experimente bewiesen, dass die genaue lichtbasierte Positionierung durch Messungen einer ToF-Kamera durchführbar ist.

Keyword: ToF-Kamera. Sichtbares Licht Positionierung. Zeitdifferenz der Ankunft. Winkel der Ankunft. Optische drahtlose Positionierung.

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List of Abbreviations

2D Two-dimensional

3D Three-dimensional

AOA Angle Of Arrival

BS Base Station

CCD Charge-Coupled Device

CDMA Code Division Multiple Access

CMOS Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor

CRA Chief Ray Angle

CRB Cramér-Rao Bound

CW-iToF Continuous-Wave-modulated iToF

dToF Direct Time-of-Flight

EM Expectation-Maximization

EMI Electromagnetic Interference

FDMA Frequency Division Multiple Access

FOV Field of View

FPGA Field Programmable Gate Array

FWHM Full Width Half Maximum

GMM Gaussian Mixture Model

GPS Global Positioning System

GT Ground Truth

HOG Histogram Of Oriented Gradient

i.i.d. Independently and Identically Distributed

IoT Internet of Things

IR Infrared

IS Image Sensor

iToF Indirect Time-of-Flight

LBS Location-Based Services

LED Light-Emitting Diode

LiDAR Light Detection And Ranging

LOS Line-Of-Sight

LUT Look-Up Table

MAI Multiple Access Interference

MLE Maximum Likelihood Estimation

MMCM Mixed-Mode Clock Manager

MPI Multipath Interference

MS Mobile Station

NIR Near-Infrared

NLOS Non-Line-Of-Sight

OOK On-Off Keying

OWP Optical Wireless Positioning

P-iToF Pulse-Modulated iToF

PD photodiode

PL Programmable Logic

PLL Phase-Locked Loop

PMMA Polymethylmethacrylate

PS Processing System

RFID Radio Frequency Identification

RMS Root Mean Square

RMSE Root Mean Squared Error

RSSI Received Signal Strength Indicator

SBI Suppression of Background Illumination

SDMA Spatial Division Multiple Access

SIFT Scale-Invariant Feature Transform

SLAM Simultaneous Localization And Mapping

SNR Signal-to-Noise Ratio

SPAD Single Photon Avalanche Diode

SSL Solid-State Lighting

SURF Speeded Up Robust Features

TCSPC Time-Correlated Single-Photon Counting

TDC Time-to-Digital Converter

TDMA Time Division Multiple Access

TDOA Time Difference Of Arrival

TOA Time Of Arrival

ToF Time-of-Flight

USB Universal Serial Bus

UV Ultraviolet

UWB Ultra-Wide Band

VCSEL Vertical Cavity Surface Emitting Laser

VLC Visible Light Communications

VLP Visible Light Positioning

VPS Visual Positioning System

Wi-Fi Wireless Fidelity

WLAN Wireless Local Area Network

WLS Weighted Least Squares

WN Wireless Network

1 Introduction

With the rapid development of technology, systems with ever larger degrees of autonomy, such as autonomous vehicles and mobile robots, are becoming mainstream. In particular, the advantages of robots are significant for repetitive and heavy work, such as in highly automated express sorting systems, where robots can ensure high efficiency, accuracy, and long-time work, in contrast to excessive human involvement that makes the system unstable. In an intelligent storage system, each robot is not simply an executor of commands but also a collector of information. By sensing the surrounding environment and exchanging information (position, speed, etc.) with nearby robots, an intelligent storage system with high efficiency, reasonable advance planning, and real-time information feedback has shown strong advantages. The gradual maturity of 5G technology and the rapid development of 6G further facilitates the overall deployment of Internet of Things (IoT). The location information of things plays an important role in mutual interaction.

Positioning technologies can be divided into outdoor and indoor positioning, depending on the application scenario. Because of the different positioning environments, the requirements for positioning precision are also different. The outdoor positioning environment comprises large volumes and has few obstacles, so positioning precision at the tens of centimeters up to one meter can satisfy the needs of most relevant applications. In contrast, indoor positioning accuracy can be affected by many obstacles, such as furniture. In contrast, the precision of indoor positioning requires a centimeter level to meet the demand of real applications. GPS-based positioning, together with navigation algorithms are mature enough to achieve positioning accuracy within the meter level in outdoor areas. GPS-based positioning systems cannot be extended to indoor areas due

to the blockage of buildings. Indoor positioning technology has been increasingly used in many industries over the past few years and plays an increasingly important role in our daily lives. With the increasing number of skyscrapers, office buildings, and shopping malls, people spend more than 80% of their time indoors, and the use of mobile robots in smart factories represented by autonomous storage systems, a GPS-independent indoor high-precision positioning system has attracted the attention of researchers.

Indoor positioning systems are mainly divided into: 1. indoor positioning systems based on computer vision technology, 2. indoor positioning systems based on wireless communication technology, 3. indoor positioning systems based on Optical Wireless Positioning (OWP) technology, where Infrared (IR) (Near-Infrared (NIR)), Ultraviolet (UV) and visible light can be used as light sources. Although the traditional radio technology has been widely used and the technology is quite mature, Visible Light Positioning (VLP) is gradually accepted by industry and scientific community because of its unique advantages. The visible light has a huge amount of unused and unregulated bandwidth, and it is independent of Electromagnetic Interference (EMI). Furthermore, optical signals cannot penetrate walls, which ensures privacy and security of communication.

In many applications, three-dimensional imaging is required because two-dimensional images cannot convey all the necessary information. An example is mobile robotics or autonomous driving, where accidents can be avoided if powerful 3D information can be captured. However, the traditional 2D imaging technology does not directly capture the distance information of the scene, so depth imaging technology has been developed. 3D vision technology can obtain the complete geometric information of real 3D scenes and realize accurate digitization for scenes, so as to achieve high-precision recognition, localization, reconstruction and other key functions of machine vision. With the release of Kinect [8] in 2010 and iPhone X [9] in 2017, 3D vision technology has turned from

a high-end technology traditionally used only in professional fields to a consumer-level product.

ToF imaging is one of the rapidly developing 3D sensing technologies that have been embraced by an increasing number of end devices in recent years. ToF cameras based on the direct ToF principle directly measure the time difference between the transmitted and received light pulses to calculate the actual distance. ToF cameras based on the indirect ToF principle calculate depth information by measuring the phase shift between the emitted periodic signal and the reflected signal. With the massive installation of Light-Emitting Diodes (LEDs) indoors and the widespread use of end devices with ToF cameras (e.g., smartphones, tablets, etc.), a hardware basis is available for combining VLC and ToF cameras to achieve indoor positioning. Through the study of VLC and ToF cameras, we have assessed the feasibility of combining VLC and ToF cameras for indoor positioning.

In this paper, we propose an indoor positioning system based on visible light localization using array of ToF pixels. We start from the mathematical model of radiation pattern of an LED module and approximate the illumination distribution based on Lambertian radiation pattern by a Gaussian distribution. Leveraging the amplitude images and depth images provided by the ToF camera, LED position information and distance information between LED and ToF module can be obtained. Indoor localization based on AOA and TDOA algorithms is considered in the experiments.

The outline of the thesis is as follows: Chapter 2 focuses on the classification of ToF cameras and compares the principles of direct and indirect ToF. In order to improve the accuracy of the distance measurements, the main error sources are listed. In this chapter we also analyze the trade-offs of ToF cameras. Chapter 3 briefly reviews the principles of existing indoor positioning techniques and compares their advantages and disadvantages.

Chapter 4 includes the existing techniques that can be used to perform VLP and their corresponding principles, with a focus on Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) algorithms. We discuss the channel transmission model for indoor visible light systems and provide the transmission gain of the Line-Of-Sight (LOS) channel. The optical power distribution is compared by means of simulations in a 4-LEDs and a 5-LEDs system model. We use least squares to solve the localization matrix equation. Moreover, we briefly review the Time Of Arrival (TOA), Time Difference Of Arrival (TDOA), Angle Of Arrival (AOA), and Image Sensor (IS)-based algorithms in conjunction with the corresponding geometric schematics. Since indoor positioning involves multiple transmitters, how to distinguish the source of the received signals needs to be considered. Another focus of this chapter is the review of four multiple access techniques applied in VLP, namely, Frequency Division Multiple Access (FDMA), Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA), Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA), Spatial Division Multiple Access (SDMA).

Chapter 5 introduces the core technologies of our proposed indoor localization system. Firstly, a workflow diagram briefly introduces the working process of the whole positioning system. Our localization system is divided into three main phases: the modulated signal transmitting phase, the mixed-signal receiving phase, and the localization phase. In this Chapter we prove that the illuminance distribution based on the Lambertian radiation pattern can be approximated by the Gaussian function in the 1D and 2D cases. We use Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) or Expectation-Maximization (EM) estimation to obtain the coordinates of the LED center point from the different distributions on the amplitude image. In this chapter, the AOA algorithm based on the lens normal matrix is presented, and the principles of TDOA based on Chan's method and TDOA based on Taylor series expansion are introduced, respectively.

In Chapter 6 we first introduce our indoor localization system model with a short

description of each system component. A computer simulation of the entire workflow is presented. We use two independent Gaussian models to simulate the distribution of the LED modules on the amplitude image, and then successfully estimate the centers of the two LEDs using the EM algorithm. The position of the ToF module is accurately estimated using the lens normal matrix of a PMD “Selene” module (resolution: 172×224). In this chapter, we also simulate the demodulation process of the ToF camera and perform the positioning simulation using the TDOA algorithm. We run 100 simulations at each test point and perform hypothesis testing. Additionally, the RMSE and the Cramér–Rao lower bound for Chan’s method, the Taylor series expansion method and the hybrid Chan/Taylor method are compared. Apart from computer simulations, tests are also conducted. We use the FPGA frequency multiplication and division method to generate five different frequencies. This chapter shows the results obtained when using the “Selene” module, featuring an IRS2877C imager, to the proposed indoor positioning system when the single LED module is located of the observed domain. As a comparison, the same test is performed using a ZESS MultiCam.

In Chapter 7 we discuss the various problems encountered in the indoor positioning system and give the corresponding solutions. We propose an improved experimental setup building upon the existing experimental setup and test results.

Chapter 8 summarizes the results of the thesis and proposes a reasonable future plan based on the results of the current work.

2 Time-of-Flight

At present, the more widely used depth acquisition techniques mainly include laser scanning, stereo vision, structured light, and the Time-of-Flight (ToF) method. The most typical representative of the laser scanning method is Light Detection And Ranging (LiDAR), whose working principle is to scan the scene point by point, in order to obtain the depth information of the object in the spatial range. The advantage of this scanning 3D imaging is that the measurement range is large, and the measurement accuracy is high. Stereo vision technology imitates the parallax imaging principle of human eyes, using cameras to obtain the left and right views of the scene from different positions, then getting the parallax and solving the depth information based on the geometric relationship between the camera and the measured scene. This method is based on image feature matching, which has high algorithmic complexity, high computational resource consumption. Feature matchin is easily disturbed by external environmental factors, such as changes in ambient light intensity, occlusions, and texture, which can cause feature matching failure or reduce measurement accuracy. Structured light is a depth acquisition technique that makes use of a projector and a 2D camera. A projector is used to emit encoded light projected onto the object, the encoded light is then captured by a 2D camera, and finally, the position and depth information of the object is solved by calculating the aberrations of the returned encoded pattern by a specific algorithm. Depending on the encoding pattern, it can be classified as stripe structured light, encoded structured light, and scattered structured light. The method has high measurement accuracy, but is easily disturbed by ambient light, resulting in poor outdoor performance, and the measurement range is short. The accuracy deteriorates as the detection distance increases. Along with the rapid development of integrated circuits and semiconductor

production processes in recent years, ToF camera has been greatly developed. This method acquires the depth information of the measured scene by encoding the time of flight of light in the measurements. Compared with LIDAR, structured light, and other depth acquisition techniques, the ToF camera has the advantages of high imaging accuracy, small size, and easy integration. Leveraging the array of ToF pixels, the ToF camera can acquire all data points simultaneously, while the laser scanner acquires data sequentially. ToF camera is playing an increasingly important role in the field of depth acquisition. The major ToF camera manufacturers include pmdtechnologies, MESA Imaging (Heptagon, ams), SoftKinetic-Optima (Sony), Basler, meerecompany, Analog Devices, Teledyne e2v, Lucid Vision Labs, Microsoft [10], Samsung, and Panasonic, among others. In Fig. 2.1 four ToF cameras are shown. ToF cameras are not only used for dense 3D mapping, but also in many fields such as gesture interaction [11][12], indoor surveillance [13], material sensing [14][15], and automated driving [16].

2.1 The Principle of Time-of-Flight

ToF systems are classified according to the specific method used to obtain the distance, and are mainly divided in Direct Time-of-Flight (dToF) and Indirect Time-of-Flight (iToF). These two methods are quite different in terms of hardware and algorithms.

2.1.1 Direct Time-of-Flight

The dToF directly measures the time difference between the transmitted and received optical pulse to calculate the actual distance. The speed of light (c) is known, and the receiver measures the time difference (Δt) of the light signal reflected back from the object's position. According to $d = \Delta t \times c/2$, the distance d can be calculated. In other words, the distance d is proportional to time difference Δt . How to accurately

(a) CamCube with 204×204 pixels and SBI from pmdtechnologies AG.

(b) From left to right—Kinect v1, Kinect v2, Azure Kinect.

(c) LUCID HELIOS ToF camera.

(d) The ToF module jointly developed by pmdtechnologies AG and Infineon Technologies for the Project Tango Smartphone.

Figure 2.1: Four ToF cameras.(Reference of pictures: (a)[1], (b)[2], (c)[3], (d)[4]).

measure Δt is the key to the implementation of the dToF technology. Because of laser safety limitations and the power consumption of the product, the ToF camera emits a limited amount of energy in the shape of a pulse of light, but this light pulse needs to cover the complete Field of View (FOV) of the sensor. Under the combined effect of low signal power and presence of ambient light, the signal is covered by noise and ambient light, and it is difficult to retrieve it due to its low amplitude, thus, leading to an error in depth estimation. The key component is the Single Photon Avalanche Diode (SPAD), which basically has the sensitivity of detecting a single photon. As soon as a

photon hits the SPAD, it will output a pulse. However, even at 850 nm and 940 nm, ambient light is still present, which means that as soon as the SPAD starts counting, photons may keep hitting the SPAD, and making it activate, and producing output pulses. Distinguishing the received photons emitted from the transmitter and reflected back by the target becomes a difficult problem. One can use an appropriate narrow-band filter so that most scene ambient light can not pass through the filter. In dToF sensors, Time-to-Digital Converters (TDCs) are typically used to measure the time of arrival of photons.

The method used in dToF is called Time-Correlated Single-Photon Counting (TC-SPC), which actually means “counting the number of photon arrivals”. The Fig. 2.2 shows a more specific scheme of the dToF system. Assume that we use the Vertical

Figure 2.2: The principle of operation of dToF from reference [5].

Cavity Surface Emitting Laser (VCSEL) on the transmitter side to emit 100 laser pulses at high rate and record the time ΔT for each pulse received by the SPAD. The distribution of time ΔT is represented in the form of a histogram, the peak ΔT is the most likely ΔT caused by the location of the target, while the other ΔT appearances may be caused by the SPAD’s noise, ambient light noise, secondary reflections returning to the sensor after multipath, etc. [5], [17], [18], [19].

In practical applications, VCSELs can emit very high frequency modulation pulses, and each pulse width can be in the picosecond (ps) to nanosecond (ns) level. SPADs can also achieve very fast corresponding speeds. The distance detection precision of dToF is essentially limited by the pulse width as $\Delta R = c \times \Delta t/2$. A VCSEL is a semiconductor laser, the response speed is very fast and can reach the ps level. Assuming that the pulse width reaches 0.1 ns, then ΔR can reach 0.015 m, that is, 15 mm detection distance precision.

Several uncertainties affect the accuracy of time difference measurements throughout the measurement process. The Root Mean Square (RMS) of total time uncertainty is given by the sum of the RMS values of the individual contributors assuming that they are all statistically independent [5].

$$\sigma_{\text{total}} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{laser}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{SPAD}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{TDC}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{other}}^2}, \quad (2.1)$$

where the components σ_{laser} , σ_{SPAD} , σ_{TDC} are the time uncertainty parameters of the laser pulse generation, the SPAD response, and the TDC circuit, respectively. σ_{other} are other statistically independent uncertainty parameters in the system, which may include the response of other electronic circuitry and the influence of pixels on each other, etc.. However, this component is insignificant in comparison with other components.

2.1.2 Indirect Time-of-Flight

The main method of iToF is to calculate the time by measuring the phase difference between the transmitted sinusoidal/pulse signal and the received sinusoidal/pulse signal, also called phase-based ToF. According to different modulation scheme, iToF methods can be generally divided into Pulse-Modulated iToF (P-iToF) and Continuous-Wave-modulated iToF (CW-iToF). The CW-iToF method resolves the depth by retrieving the phase of a sinusoidal signal, while the P-iToF resolves the depth by resolving the phase

of a pulsed signal. Since the phase shift of the modulated light is proportional to the distance between the object and the camera, the phase shift can be used to measure the distance.

Pulse-Modulated iToF

In the P-iToF system, the light source emits light pulses for a brief period T_P , and the maximum detection distance $d_{MAX} = T_P \times c/2$ can be calculated based on the speed of light c . The emitted signal and the received signal are shown in Fig. 2.3. One sensor A works with the same frequency waveform as the emitted signal, and one sensor B operates with the same frequency waveform as the emitted signal, but with a phase difference of π . Sensor A and sensor B are alternately switching to integrate the received signal, and they respectively receive a part of the returned signal. According to the accumulated charge after integration time, the distance between the camera and the scene is calculated as:

$$d = \frac{1}{2}c \cdot T_P \cdot \left(\frac{B}{A + B} \right) \quad (2.2)$$

But, in fact, sensors A and B receive not only the reflected light but also the ambient light signal. Assume that sensor C is activated when no light pulse is emitted and collects only the ambient light signal. Eq.2.3 will become:

$$d = \frac{1}{2}c \cdot T_P \cdot \left(\frac{B - C}{A + B - 2C} \right) \quad (2.3)$$

Continuous-Wave-Modulated iToF

CW-iToF usually uses sinusoidal modulation. The phase shift of the sinusoidally-modulated light is proportional to the distance between the object and the camera. Fig. 2.4 shows the operating principle of the CW-iToF system.

Figure 2.3: Illustration of the principle operation of of P-iToF from reference [6].

Figure 2.4: The principle of CW-iToF: The phase delay between emitted and reflected signals is measured to calculate the distance from each sensor pixel to target objects.

Considering single frequency modulation, the mathematical representation of the original modulated light signal $s(t)$ and reflected signal $r(t)$ is as follows

$$s(t) = 1 + \lambda \cos(\omega t) \quad (2.4)$$

$$r(t) = A \cos(\omega t - \phi) + B \quad (2.5)$$

Here, λ is the modulation depth and ω is the angular frequency of modulation of the light source. A and B are the amplitude and intensity offset of the reflection, respectively. Furthermore, the influence of background light is modeled by B . ϕ is the delay between the transmitted signal and the reflected signal. The distance between the target and the camera is given by the following equation,

$$d = \frac{c}{4\pi f_{mod}} \phi \quad (2.6)$$

where c is the speed of light. A continuous-wave ToF sensor measures the correlation function between the two signals [20][21], and samples at the time τ_q are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} C_\omega(\tau_q) &= (s(t) \otimes r(t))(\tau) \\ &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T [1 + \lambda \cdot \cos(\omega t + \omega\tau_q)] [A \cos(\omega t - \phi) + B] dt \\ &= \frac{\omega}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi/\omega} [\lambda A \cos(\omega t + \omega\tau_q) \cos(\omega t - \phi) + B] dt \\ &= \frac{\omega}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi/\omega} \left\{ \frac{\lambda A}{2} [\cos(\omega t + \omega\tau_q - \omega t + \phi) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \cos(\omega t + \omega\tau_q + \omega t - \phi)] + B \right\} dt \\ &= \frac{\lambda A}{2} \cos(\omega\tau_q + \phi) + B \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

where \otimes denotes cross-correlation. In order to recover all the parameters, only three measurements are needed, although in practice four measurements are usually used. By

using the “four-phases algorithm” [22], we can calculate the amplitude A , the phase shift ϕ , and the offset B . Using four samples at $\tau_q = \pi q / 4\omega$ with $q=0, \dots, 3$:

$$A = \sqrt{(C_\omega(\tau_3) - C_\omega(\tau_1))^2 + (C_\omega(\tau_0) - C_\omega(\tau_2))^2} / 2\lambda \quad (2.8)$$

$$\tan \phi = \left(\frac{C_\omega(\tau_3) - C_\omega(\tau_1)}{C_\omega(\tau_0) - C_\omega(\tau_2)} \right) \quad (2.9)$$

$$B = \frac{C_\omega(\tau_0) + C_\omega(\tau_1) + C_\omega(\tau_2) + C_\omega(\tau_3)}{4} \quad (2.10)$$

2.2 Measurement Errors

Although the performance of ToF cameras has also been greatly improved and has been widely used in cell phones and other terminal devices in recent years, there are still errors in the process of depth measurement, as with traditional sensors.

ToF raw data is not reliable without calibration because of a number of sources of systematic errors in the measurement process, such as lens distortion, integration time, sensor temperature drift, signal distortion, etc. In addition to these errors that can be calibrated, there are also non-systematic errors such as Multipath Interference (MPI), motion artifacts, and ambient light, which cannot be calibrated.

Lens Distortion

When the camera is aimed at the center of the object, theoretically, the center of the object will be imaged in the center of the camera. However, due to errors in the camera assembly process or the deviations in the camera structure, the actual imaging is not in the center of the camera but will appear at a certain offset. In addition, When imaging an object with a straight edge on the edge of the picture, it can be observed

that the edge of the picture appears curved inward or outward, which is often referred to as barrel or pincushion distortion. The purpose of lens calibration is mainly to solve the problems of optical center shift and distortion caused by the unavoidable differences in the manufacturing and assembly process. Lens calibration precedes all other calibrations, which need to build upon an ideal optical image.

Systematic Wiggling Error

A major systematic error of ToF cameras is the wiggling error. It is also known as harmonic aliasing or circular error. In the ideal case, the measured distance is considered to be the actual distance. However, due to the limitation of hardware and cost, the transmitted signal is not a perfect sinusoidal signal. Besides the fundamental wave signal, it may also contain higher order harmonic components. Therefore, the imperfect sinusoidal signal in the demodulation process causes periodic errors between the measured phase difference and the ideal phase difference. The wiggling error compensation is often performed by building an error Look-Up Table (LUT) [23][24]. This method has high accuracy, but the accuracy of compensation depends on the size of the error LUT. The compensation time depends on the implemented scheme. In the implementation in [23], the compensation time is far less than the real-time acquisition time, which makes it possible to acquire dynamic scenes.

Integration Time

Increasing or decreasing the integration time can have an effect on the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). Shorter integration times result in missing information due to insufficient SNR and longer integration times result in saturation, so a reasonable integration time is especially important to obtain a reliable depth measurement [25].

Temperature-Related Error

Due to the heat-sensitive properties of semiconductor materials, temperature changes can affect the performance of the sensor and thus the accuracy of the measurement. The temperature change can also be divided into external and internal temperature change. The main contributor to the internal temperature change is that the temperature of the sensor chip rises with the increase of operating time. The depth estimates also increase with temperature, but the camera errors will also be stable as the temperature gradually stabilizes [24][22]. Therefore, a warm-up time for the ToF camera needs to be considered. External temperature changes also have an impact on distance measurements. Hence, the camera should be operated in an environment with a stable temperature and be calibrated for temperature. Without temperature calibration, it is easy to imagine that for the same distance, as the temperature rises, the depth measured by the ToF camera becomes larger and larger.

Amplitude-related errors

The accuracy of the measurement is related to the amplitude of the received signal. Low amplitude often appears at the edge of the image because the emitted light power decays radially, resulting in an overestimation of depth. This phenomenon can be observed in Fig. 6 of [22] and in Fig. 19 in [26]. The resolution of the ToF cameras does not change as the distance increases, the accuracy drops due to the lower amplitude (fewer incoming photons) as the distance increases. Consequently, different objects at the same position will have different depth measurements due to their own reflectivity.

Multipath Interference

One of the most common problems the ToF technology faces is MPI[27][28][29]. Light is reflected multiple times in the target scene, and an object reflects not only

the modulated light emitted by the camera, but also light from other indirect paths. The interference between reflected light from multiple sources can lead to errors in the depth measurement. There are four general sources of multipath effects. First, the highly reflective objects in the target scene, for example, smooth walls, mirrors, etc. The second category is transparent objects or translucent objects, for example, glass. The third category includes corners and corner-like objects. Each point on the wall will generally receive reflected light from other points and will be partially reflected back to the camera [26]. The last category includes the camera's internal lens system, such as multiple reflections of photons between the lens and ToF pixels.

Motion artifacts

Dynamic scenes and relative motion between the ToF camera and the scenes can cause motion artifacts in the depth images. The ToF camera requires a certain amount of time for acquiring each of the raw images required to obtain a depth image. After the integration time of the ToF camera, the calculated phase shift is inaccurate due to the change of relative position between consecutive raw image acquisitions, which leads to wrong depth estimation, especially on borders of objects [30].

Ambient Light

Unless the camera operates in a dark room, the scene reflects not only modulated light from the ToF camera, but also ambient light. Sunlight is the most prominent type of ambient light in outdoor scenes. Since outdoor sunlight contains infrared light components, these infrared light components can still lead to measurement errors even though the components are not modulated. Moreover, the sunlight intensity is much higher than the modulated light intensity, leading to saturation risk.

2.3 Trade-offs

Since the ToF camera is a complex system that consists of different components, for a better performance of the camera, we should have a good understanding of the different components, including the illumination system, lens components, and power supply. Meanwhile, the camera's performance is also related to the cost budget and the application requirement. The variance of the depth measurement can be summarized by this equation [31][32][33]:

$$\sigma = \frac{c}{4\sqrt{2}\pi f} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{B}}{c_d A} \quad (2.11)$$

where A is the reflected amplitude. B is the offset, which is related to ambient light and temperature. c_d is the modulation contrast, which describes the ability of ToF sensors to separate and collect photo-electrons. f is the modulation frequency and c is the speed of light. From Eq.2.11 we know that the depth measurement variance is mainly related to A , B , f and c_d .

The Reflected Amplitude A

The greater the reflected amplitude A , the higher the depth measurement accuracy. To increase the reflected amplitude A , increasing the power of the illumination light is a desirable option. However, it also increases the power consumption and heat generation. If the reflectivity of the measured object is high, the corresponding reflection amplitude is also high. The quality of the lens also influences the collection efficiency, which consequently affects the reflected amplitude A . Increasing the integration time is also a common way to increase the reflected amplitude A . However, increasing the exposure time will lead to a decrease in the maximum frame rate and may even cause overexposure in bright areas.

The Offset B

The lower the offset B, the higher the depth measurement accuracy. The two most important factors for offset B are ambient light and temperature. Ambient light, such as sunlight can cause an increment of offset B, potentially causing saturation. A very narrow bandpass filter centered on the wavelength of the illumination system is worth considering. High temperatures can cause more free electrons that are collected, yielding an increased offset B.

The Modulation Frequency f

The higher the modulation frequency, the higher the depth measurement accuracy. High modulation frequency can cause two consequences: high energy consumption and low maximum measurable distance. Since the phase is periodic in 2π , when the measurement goes beyond 2π , the measurement goes onto the next phase cycle, this is called phase wrapping. The maximum measurable distance is defined as:

$$d_{\max} = \frac{c}{2f} \quad (2.12)$$

Increasing the modulation frequency leads to a higher accuracy but decreases the maximum measurable distance. Multi-frequency technology enables the maximum measurement range to be extended while maintaining high accuracy. Two or more frequencies are used in multi-frequency techniques, and different frequencies have different unambiguous ranges. We can then compare depth measurements obtained at different frequencies to find the correct unwrapped distance that would be common to all frequencies. In the case of two single frequencies f_1 and f_2 , the extended non-ambiguous range is described as [31]:

$$R = \frac{c}{2 \cdot (f_2 - f_1)} \quad (2.13)$$

where c is the speed of light and $f_2 - f_1$ is called the beat frequency.

The Modulation Contrast c_d

The modulation contrast c_d is a unitless parameter describing the modulation and demodulation performance of the system. The roll-off frequency refers to the maximum modulation frequency at which the illumination system in the ToF camera works properly. In the case of high frequencies, when the frequency is greater than the roll-off frequency [32], the modulated contrast attenuates with decreasing optical power. Thereby, ToF cameras with high roll-off frequencies provide high accuracy.

3 Indoor Positioning Technologies

In recent years, in the context of “Industry 4.0”, more and more manufacturing are gradually becoming intelligent. A lot of mobile agents play an important role in the smart manufacturing or smart storage system, and their accurate indoor positions is one of the keys to ensure the operation of the smart system. A typical positioning technology is the Global Positioning System (GPS), which is widely used in many outdoor applications. Compared with GPS, standalone cellular systems play an important role in positioning because of their strong signal, large user base, and bi-directional transmission function, although their coverage area is small. The rapid development of wireless positioning technology has enabled the introduction of Location-Based Services (LBS) in people’s daily life [34]. Although the GPS system can better solve the outdoor positioning problem, in indoor environments, the satellite signal drops rapidly due to the obstruction of walls and other obstacles, resulting in low positioning accuracy [35][36][37]. With the continuous development of urbanization, people spend almost 80%-90% of their time in indoor environments [38][39]. The demand for indoor positioning services has risen, and indoor positioning is mostly used in large shopping centers, museums, libraries, etc. Due to the portability of smart endpoint device, indoor positioning technologies based on smart endpoint device are becoming more and more mature, such as indoor positioning based on smartphones in large shopping malls [40].

Currently, the most used indoor positioning technologies are ultrasonic technology, IR technology, Bluetooth technology, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology, Ultra-Wide Band (UWB) technology, Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi) positioning technology, visual positioning technology, LiDAR-based Simultaneous Localization And Mapping (SLAM) technology, etc. The comparison of accuracy and cost between different indoor

positioning technologies is shown in Fig. 3.1. In Tab. 3.1, the accuracy, complexity, and cost of different indoor positioning techniques are listed. The advantages and disadvantages of each technique are compared and some examples are given.

Figure 3.1: Accuracy-cost chart of positioning technology.

Wi-Fi

Wi-Fi technology based on the IEEE 802.11 communication protocol is one of the solutions for indoor positioning. Wi-Fi takes advantage of Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) access points as beacons to locate mobile endpoints. There are many Wi-Fi-based localization solutions, such as AOA [60], TOA [61], TDOA [62], RSSI [63], etc. In particular, the distance between the transmitter and the terminal device is estimated by measuring the propagation time of the signal (TOA). Since the speed of light is very large, a small-time error can lead to a large positioning error, so the transmitter and

Indoor Technologies	Accuracy	Complexity	Cost	Advantages	Disadvantages	Examples
Wi-Fi	1-5 m	Low	Low	Low hardware costs	Limited positioning accuracy; Affected by environmental factors	[41][42][43]
Infrared	0.01-0.1 m	Low	High	Low power consumption	Short-range; Affected by temperature, light; Cost for extra hardware	[44][45]
Ultrasonic	0.1-1 m	Medium	High	Low implementation difficulty	Temperature-dependent	[46]
Bluetooth	2-5 m	Low	Low	Large number of users; Low power consumption	Short-range; Low accuracy	[47][48]
RFID	1-2 m	Low	Medium	Moderate cost	MPI; Need reader, Tag	[49][50][51]
UWB	0.06-0.1 m	Medium	High	Excellent accuracy	Short-range; High costs	[52][53]
Visual	0.05-1.2 m	High	High	Scene reconstruction	Sensitive to ambient light; Image-dependent	[54][55]
LiDAR-SLAM	0.01-0.1 m	High	High	Excellent accuracy	High costs	[56][57]
Visible Light	0.01-0.1 m	Low	Low	Dual use of lighting infrastructure	Backbone sometimes required; LED-layout-dependent	[58][59]

Table 3.1: Comparison of indoor positioning technologies.

the terminal device must be strictly synchronized. In addition, there will be strong MPI during signal propagation due to the complexity of indoor environments, resulting in unreliable final positioning estimation. Fingerprint-based positioning methods are also widely used in indoor positioning [64][42][65]. First, the RSS of different positions in the room is collected to establish a fingerprint database, then the RSS of the received signal and the fingerprint database are compared. Through fingerprint matching the position of the receiver can be estimated [42][66].

Infrared

The infrared indoor positioning system mainly comprises an infrared transmitter and infrared receiver. The target carries an IR emitter that automatically emits modulated IR, and the IR signal is received by several IR receivers located inside the room. The Active Badge location system is based on this method to achieve indoor positioning [67]. IR positioning system stability is not strong, and IR light can be easily disturbed by external factors such as temperature and light. Since the accuracy of the IR positioning is related to the density of IR receivers, a high number of receivers installed in the room can also lead to high costs.

Ultrasonic

Ultrasonic positioning technology uses sound signals with frequencies above 20 KHz to calculate the time difference between the transmitter and receiver. With the speed of sound, we can obtain distance information and then use the trilateral positioning method to estimate the position. Ultrasonic positioning technology is a simple system, but it requires a large amount of hardware equipment to be allocated indoors, which can be very expensive. On the other hand, the speed of sound is not constant, but given by equation:

$$c_{\text{sound}} = \sqrt{\gamma RT} \quad (3.1)$$

where the γ is the heat capacity ratio, which is defined as the ratio between the specific heat at constant pressure and the one at constant volume. R is the gas constant and T is temperature. γ and R are both related to the humidity in the air. The positioning error caused by the variation of sound velocity due to factors such as room temperature and humidity needs to be taken into account.

Bluetooth

Bluetooth is a wireless technology that enables the exchange of information or data over short distances. Bluetooth positioning technology is also one of the popular positioning technologies nowadays. The stronger the Bluetooth signal, the closer the distance between the Bluetooth receiver and the transmitter. Bluetooth-based positioning generally uses RSSI [68] [69] or fingerprint method [70] [71]. With the rapid development of mobile phones and other terminal devices, Bluetooth has become one of their basic functionalities, so the positioning based on Bluetooth technology has a wide user base. The major technology companies have also invested in indoor positioning based on Bluetooth technology, with Apple and Google being the most prominent. In 2003, Apple released the *iBeacon* protocol, which was specifically used for Bluetooth positioning [72] [73], and Google launched the *Eddystone* [74] standard in 2005. Despite the widespread use of Bluetooth technology, it still has e.g., its short transmission distance. If the purpose of wide coverage, high precision positioning is to be achieved, many Bluetooth devices need to be arranged; Bluetooth signals are susceptible to EMI from other wireless signals.

Radio Frequency Identification

An RFID system consists of three main parts: reader, tag, and database. The tag contains location identification information, the reader connects to the database by wireless communication and transmits RF signals in the room. When the tag enters the range of the reader, the signal strength information, time information or angle information of

the tag and the reader are measured to determine the position [75] [76] [77]. *Land Marc* [78] and *Spot On* [50] indoor positioning systems are the main representatives of indoor positioning using RFID technology. The short positioning distance and the effect of EMI are the shortcomings of the RFID system. Since the positioning accuracy depends on the database, it is difficult to provide a common set of database models for different indoor scenarios.

Ultra-Wide Band

Instead of using carriers as in traditional communication systems, UWB transmits data by sending and receiving very narrow pulses with sub-nanosecond or microsecond duration [79][80]. The bandwidth determines the resolution of the distance range. Since it has a large bandwidth, the difficult problem of signal attenuation affecting positioning accuracy during propagation, typical from wireless technology, is solved. Because it is insensitive to channel attenuation, it can achieve indoor close range accurate positioning. The principle of UWB positioning technology is to install some base stations that can receive UWB pulse signals indoors, and the target carries a transmitter that can transmit UWB pulse signals, and the position is calculated by means of TDOA [79][81]. UWB is also short-range positioning, it is expensive if a large range of positioning is desired.

Visual

Image sensor-based visual positioning technology is a positioning technology that has received much attention in recent years. The Visual Positioning System (VPS) uses image sensors to capture environmental information and derive position information based on that obtained information. The process of reconstructing a virtual scene using data acquired from image sensors and building an image fingerprint database based on descriptors of the scene structure is usually considered the training stage. The images can be represented as several feature points containing descriptors. The set of descriptors of

all feature points of all image is the so-called fingerprint database. The descriptors can be calculated by Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF), Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) or Histogram Of Oriented Gradient (HOG) algorithm. The location estimation can be performed by matching the descriptors of feature points, and this process is the testing stage [54] [55].

LiDAR-based SLAM

SLAM is a solution or technology that helps robots achieve positioning and map construction. It is inaccurate to estimate the robot's position simply based on its motion, because the robot's odometer usually has some errors. Usually, a distance measuring device such as LIDAR is used to obtain the environmental information (a point cloud) and then fuse it with the odometer information to obtain the robot's position more accurately. The extended Kalman filter is the core of SLAM, which continuously estimates the robot's position, pose and the surrounding environment information, and through iterative operations, the robot's position can be estimated more accurately. Only with a good position and pose estimate can the individual point clouds be stitched together to generate a global 3D map [57] [56].

Visible Light

A visible light indoor positioning system is based on the common indoor white LEDs to realize the positioning. While the LED is on, the light signal carrying the position information is emitted. The receiver at the unknown position receives the signal and demodulates it. Through TOA, AOA and RSSI, the position of the target can be calculated. VLP has not only the function of positioning while illuminating but also obvious advantages when compared to RF wireless communication methods in terms of electromagnetic radiation, security, etc. VLP is free from EMI, while the accuracy of RF wireless positioning is influenced by EMI. Visible Light Communications (VLC) is

used in many application fields, such as airplanes, hospitals, and other EMI-sensitive applications.

4 Visible Light Positioning

With the development of Solid-State Lighting (SSL) technology, white LEDs are becoming more and more popular in lighting systems. Compared to traditional incandescent lighting, LEDs have significant advantages in energy efficiency and lifetime [82] [83] [84]. The energy consumption of LEDs is at least 75% less than that of incandescent lighting, and the lifetime is at least 25 times longer than that of incandescent lighting [85]. The spectrum of visible light is between 400 and 800 THz. Many existing applications dominate most of the RF frequency spectrum and the available regions of the spectrum are becoming increasingly scarce. However, visible light has a large bandwidth, and great potential for applications [84] [85] [86]. The high-frequency switching characteristics of LEDs provide the possibility of a new communication system [87]. Since light cannot pass through walls, the receiver does not receive interference signals from the adjacent room, so visible light positioning has high accuracy and security. Because of the advantages of LEDs, according to expert predictions, LEDs will dominate 75% of the lighting market in 2030 [88], but our proposed method apply to all type of OWP system.

VLC is not affected by EMI and can realize the functions of indoor illumination and indoor positioning at the same time. VLC has received great attention as a new type of indoor access point technology [89]. The method of indoor positioning using the modulated white LEDs as the emitters is known as VLP. Two types of devices are typically used at the receiver terminal, namely, a photodiode (PD) or an IS. Due to the many advantages of visible light positioning system, we mainly introduce the visible light based OWP.

4.1 The Principle of Positioning Technologies

Many different techniques can be used in VLP. The main trilateral localization methods are TOA, TDOA, and RSSI algorithm. The triangulation localization methods are AOA algorithm and image sensor-based algorithm.

4.1.1 Received Signal Strength Indicator

The RSSI algorithm uses a PD to measure the intensity of the visible light signal emitted by the LED to estimate the location of the receiver. It is a channel-transmission-model-based positioning algorithm. In VLC systems, the receiver and transmitter are linked by LOS and Non-Line-Of-Sight (NLOS), but the LOS dominates. The LOS and the NLOS links between LED and PD are shown in Fig. 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Channel transmission model for an indoor visible light system.

Assuming that the LED radiation pattern follows the Lambertian radiation pattern [90], the gain between LED and PD from LOS channel can be expressed as:

$$H(r, \phi, \psi) = A_{\text{PD}} \frac{(m+1)}{2\pi r^2} \cos^m(\phi) \cos(\psi) T(\psi) G(\psi) \text{rect}\left(\frac{2\psi}{\text{FOV}}\right) \quad (4.1)$$

where m denotes the Lambertian parameter, which can be obtained from the LED view semi-angle at half power $\phi_{1/2}$: $m = -\frac{\ln 2}{\ln \cos \phi_{1/2}}$. r is the distance between the LED and the PD. A_{PD} is the detector physical area of the PD. ϕ is the radiation angle of the LED and ψ is the incidence angle about the PD. $T(\psi)$ and $G(\psi)$ represent the optical filter gain and the optical concentrator gain, respectively. The maximum of ψ is equal to the FOV of PD. The expression of the rectangular function is:

$$\text{rect}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } |x| \leq 1 \\ 0 & \text{for } |x| > 1 \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

When the transmitting power P_{Tx} of LED is given, the receiving power P_{Rx} of PD can be expressed as:

$$P_{\text{Rx}} = P_{\text{Tx}} H(r, \phi, \psi) \quad (4.3)$$

When the optical signal is within the FOV of the PD, substituting Eq. 4.1 into Eq. 4.3 yields:

$$P_{\text{Rx}} = P_{\text{Tx}} \cdot A_{\text{PD}} \frac{(m+1)}{2\pi r^2} \cos^m(\phi) \cos(\psi) T(\psi) G(\psi) \quad (4.4)$$

Let suppose that $T(\psi)$ and $G(\psi)$ do not vary, then we suppose $C = P_{\text{Rx}} \cdot A_{\text{PD}} \frac{(m+1)}{2\pi} T(\psi) G(\psi)$, then Eq. 4.4 is further expressed as:

$$P_{\text{Rx}} = \frac{C}{r^2} \cos^m(\phi) \cos(\psi) \quad (4.5)$$

where C is a constant. The received signal power is inversely proportional to the square

of the distance. If the LED and PD are parallel, ϕ and ψ are identical. The Eq. 4.5 can be simplified as:

$$P_{Rx} = \frac{C}{r^2} \cos^{m+1}(\phi) \quad (4.6)$$

The system model for indoor positioning is shown in Fig. 4.2. The size of this room is 3 m in length, 3 m in width and 3 m in height. The origin is on the floor at the front left of the room. The receiver is placed at the height of 1 m from the ground, and the receiver and transmitter are parallel to each other. The central LED is located at TX5 (1.5 m, 1.5 m, 3 m). The remaining four LEDs are located at TX1 (0.5 m, 0.5 m, 3 m), TX2 (0.5 m, 2.5 m, 3 m), TX3 (2.5 m, 0.5 m, 3 m) and TX4 (2.5 m, 2.5 m, 3 m). The simulation parameters of the indoor VLP system are shown in Tab. 4.1.

Figure 4.2: 3-D view of the a setup for a OWP system comprising five LEDs and a receiver.

According to Eq. 4.6 and the parameters from Tab. 4.1, the power of the received light at the receiver can be estimated. Fig. 4.3(a) shows the power distribution in the room under 4-LEDs layout. The power distribution of light under 5-LEDs layout is shown in Fig. 4.3(b). Comparing Fig. 4.3(a) and Fig. 4.3(b), we confirmed that the power distribution is influenced by the layout of LEDs [91]. Adding LEDs at appropriate locations can effectively improve the power distribution of the system.

(a) The power distribution of received light under 4-LEDs layout (without the central one). (b) The power distribution of received light under 5-LEDs layout.

Figure 4.3: Comparison of the power distribution of received light under simulation

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value</i>
Room size ($L \times W \times H$)	3 m \times 3 m \times 3 m
Semi-angle at half-power of LED $\phi_{1/2}$	30°
Optical power of LED P_{R_x}	0.5 W
Height of receiver	1 m
FOV of the PD	90°
Area of the PD A_{PD}	1 cm ²
Gain of optical filter $T_S(\psi)$	1
Optical concentrator gain $G(\psi)$	1
Photoelectric transformation efficiency r	0.35 A/W

Table 4.1: Simulation parameters of the indoor VLP system setup.

In the RSSI algorithm, the receiver needs to acquire signals from at least three transmitters. The coordinates of the transmitters are known as $TX_i = (x_i, y_i, z_i)$, $i \in (1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$, where n is the number of transmitters. The coordinates of the receiver is $RX = (x_r, y_r, z_r)$, where z_r is known. The distances between each transmitter and the

receiver can be expressed as:

$$d_i = \sqrt{(x_i - x_r)^2 + (y_i - y_r)^2 + (z_i - z_r)^2} \quad (4.7)$$

where d can be derived from the Eq. 4.6. Using three transmitters, we obtain:

$$\begin{cases} d_1^2 = (x_1 - x_r)^2 + (y_1 - y_r)^2 + (z_1 - z_r)^2 \\ d_2^2 = (x_2 - x_r)^2 + (y_2 - y_r)^2 + (z_2 - z_r)^2 \\ d_3^2 = (x_3 - x_r)^2 + (y_3 - y_r)^2 + (z_3 - z_r)^2 \end{cases} \quad (4.8)$$

Since all LEDs are fixed to the ceiling and the height of the receiver from the ground is constant, i.e. $z_i = 3$ m, $z_r = 1$ m, so the Eq. 4.8 can be simplified to the form of a matrix:

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{B} \quad (4.9)$$

where $\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 - x_1 & y_2 - y_1 \\ x_3 - x_1 & y_3 - y_1 \\ x_3 - x_2 & y_3 - y_2 \end{bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} x_r \\ y_r \end{bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} (d_1^2 - d_2^2 + x_2^2 + y_2^2 - x_1^2 - y_1^2) / 2 \\ (d_1^2 - d_3^2 + x_3^2 + y_3^2 - x_1^2 - y_1^2) / 2 \\ (d_2^2 - d_3^2 + x_3^2 + y_3^2 - x_2^2 - y_2^2) / 2 \end{bmatrix}$.

\mathbf{A} and \mathbf{Q} are known, and \mathbf{X} is to be solved. This type of matrix equation are generally solved by using the least-squares method [92] [93]. In brief, the idea of least-squares is to minimize the sum of squares of the distances between the observed and estimated points. The vector of residuals \mathbf{r} is defined as:

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X} \quad (4.10)$$

The sum of the squares of the residuals is written as:

$$f(X) = \mathbf{r}^2 = (\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X})^2 = (\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X})^T(\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}) \quad (4.11)$$

We find the minimum value of $f(\mathbf{X})$ by taking the derivative equal to zero,

$$\frac{df(\mathbf{X})}{d(\mathbf{X})} = 2\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A} \mathbf{X} - 2\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{0} \quad (4.12)$$

\mathbf{X} can be obtained as:

$$\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{B} \quad (4.13)$$

Eq. 4.7 is the basic equation of a sphere, and we can also analyze the position of the receiver from a geometric perspective. Considering only the Two-dimensional (2D) case, as shown in Fig. 4.4, the coordinates of the transmitter are the coordinates of the center of the circle, and the distance between the transmitter and the receiver is the diameter corresponding circle, the intersection of the three circles is the location of the receiver. In reality, the distance between the transmitter and receiver is always estimated with errors, which means that the three circles do not intersect perfectly at one point. Two typical errors due to over- and under-estimated distances between the transmitter and receiver are shown in Fig.4.5(a) and Fig.4.5(b).

Figure 4.4: The geometric principle of RSSI trilateral positioning method.

(a) Over-intersection between each other. (b) Under-intersection between each other.

Figure 4.5: Geometric diagram of two typical errors using the trilateration algorithm.

4.1.2 Time of Arrival

The principle of TOA is to calculate the time difference Δt between the transmitter and the receiver and, using the principle of invariance of the speed of light c , the distance between the transmitter and the receiver as $d = c\Delta t$. According to the trilateral positioning method, Eq. 4.7 is again derived. The RSSI algorithm and the TOA algorithm differ only in the method of obtaining the distance estimation. The RSSI algorithm obtains distance estimates by power of the received signal, while the TOA algorithm uses time differences to obtain distances. A small time error can lead to a significant distance error due to the very high speed of light. Therefore, obtaining an accurate time difference is the key to improved positioning accuracy. The TOA algorithm requires accurate clock synchronization between the transmitter and receiver, which results in additional costs and system complexity.

4.1.3 Time Difference of Arrival

In indoor positioning, the TOA is very small due to the short distance between transmitter and receiver. This makes the TOA technique difficult to be deployed since it requires very precise clock synchronization. Compared with TOA, TDOA is more easily implementable in the field of indoor positioning. In the TDOA algorithm, the requirement of synchronization between transmitter and receiver is no longer necessary, but synchronization between different transmitters is required [94].

The principle of the TDOA localization method is as follows: One transmitter is set as the reference transmitter. The distance difference between the receiver and the reference transmitter and between the receiver and other transmitters can be derived by measuring the arrival time difference. The measured value of TDOA geometrically corresponds to a hyperbola with the reference transmitter and the positioning transmitter as the focal point. Therefore, TDOA is also called hyperbolic positioning [95], as shown in Fig. 4.6. The coordinates of the three transmitters are known $TX_i = (x_i, y_i, z_i)$, $i \in (1, 2, 3)$. The time received by the receiver from the three transmitters is t_i , $i \in (1, 2, 3)$. If the distance difference between RX to TX_1 and TX_2 can be derived from the time difference, one hyperbola is determined. Similarly, the distance difference between RX to TX_1 and TX_3 can be known. The receiver should be located at the intersection of the two sets of hyperbolas with the reference transmitter as the focal point.

$$\begin{cases} |t_3 - t_1| \cdot c = \sqrt{(x_3 - x_r)^2 + (y_3 - y_r)^2} - \sqrt{(x_1 - x_r)^2 + (y_1 - y_r)^2} \\ |t_2 - t_1| \cdot c = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_r)^2 + (y_2 - y_r)^2} - \sqrt{(x_1 - x_r)^2 + (y_1 - y_r)^2} \end{cases} \quad (4.14)$$

Figure 4.6: The geometric principle of TDOA hyperbolic positioning.

4.1.4 Angle of Arrival

In the AOA positioning algorithm, the receiver obtains the arrival direction of the signal and then calculates the angular relationship between the receiver and the transmitter. With the help of trigonometric functions, the receiver's position can be determined. The coordinate system is constructed according to Fig. 4.7. The coordinates of the projection of the transmitters in the receiver plane are RX_i' , $i \in (1, 2, 3 \dots n)$, n is the number of LEDs. The angles between the projection of the transmitter on the receiver plane and the receiver are ϕ_i , $i \in (1, 2, 3 \dots n)$. From the coordinates of the transmitter and receiver and the corresponding trigonometric relationship, it is possible to obtain the position from equations of the form:

$$\tan \phi_i = \frac{y_r - y_i}{x_r - x_i}, i \in (1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (4.15)$$

After simplification, we get:

$$x_r \cdot \tan \phi_i - y_r = x_i \cdot \tan \phi_i - y_i, i \in (1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (4.16)$$

Figure 4.7: The geometric principle of the AOA positioning algorithm.

It can be transformed into the form of a matrix:

$$\mathbf{V}\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{Q} \quad (4.17)$$

where $\mathbf{V} = [\tan \phi_i, -1]$, $\mathbf{X} = [x_r, y_r]^T$, $\mathbf{Q} = [x_i \cdot \tan \phi_i - y_i]$. The matrix equation can be solved using the least-squares method. Although the AOA algorithm seems simple, the angle acquisition requires additional hardware support. We only discussed the algorithm of AOA in the 2D case, but in 3D positioning it is also necessary to know the elevation angle ψ_i , $i \in (1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$, the positioning algorithm is complex and easily affected by the external environment.

4.1.5 Image Sensor

Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor (CMOS) and Charge-Coupled Device (CCD)-based IS can also be used as receivers in VLP. The image sensor captures the

LEDs within the FOV through the lens, which images them on a 2D plane. The camera is positioned by projective geometry and trigonometric relationships using information about the position of the LEDs in the environment and their imaging points on the imaging sensor. Two IS-based visible light localization systems are presented in [96] and [97], and their system model diagrams are shown in Fig. 4.8.

(a) Projective geometry for indoor (b) LED projection model, LEDs in positioning using image sensors (ref- the world coordinate system are pro- erence [96]). jected onto the image plane through a lens.(reference [97]).

Figure 4.8: The geometric schematic diagram of image-sensor-based positioning algorithm

4.2 Multiple Access Technology

One of the key issues faced by VLP is to ensure that the positioning target correctly receives the signals sent by the LEDs. In the positioning techniques described above, at least two LEDs need to be used. In order to improve the accuracy of indoor positioning, a large number of LEDs are used in practice, and the layout of the LEDs is denser, which leads to overlapping coverage of the LEDs and interference between the signals, so that the receiver needs to distinguish the signals from different LEDs. Therefore, multiple access techniques need to be taken into account in indoor positioning systems.

Depending on the type of receiver, four different multiple access technologies are widely used for indoor positioning: SDMA, TDMA, FDMA, and CDMA.

4.2.1 Frequency Division Multiple Access

The FDMA technique divides the channel bandwidth into several narrower non-overlapping sub-channels, each of which is assigned to an LED. The LED signals, modulated at different frequencies, are continuous in the time domain but separated in the frequency domain. The receiver can distinguish between different LEDs in the frequency domain via correlation detection techniques. By using the same carrier frequency as the modulation frequency of the LEDs, the receiver can distinguish the LEDs and retrieve the data.

4.2.2 Code Division Multiple Access

CDMA is a multiple access technology using On-Off Keying (OOK) for communication [98]. With CDMA, each LED has its own unique code, an orthogonal (synchronous) or pseudo-random (asynchronous) code is used to encode it for spread-spectrum purposes. The receiver knows all the transmit codes and uses them to decode the mixed signals. After decoding, the receiver is able to distinguish the LEDs and obtain their information. Decoding the incoming (mixed) signal with the appropriate code allows retrieving the signal from the desired LED, annihilating the contributions of the others, due to the low-cross-correlation between codes. In asynchronous systems, incomplete orthogonality due to random offset can lead to Multiple Access Interference (MAI). MAI has an influence on the correction of RSSI and thus on the accuracy of positioning [99].

4.2.3 Time Division Multiple Access

With TDMA, every LED has its own unique time slot, and these time slots are not overlapped. Each LED only sends information during its own time slot and waits during other time slots. Precise clock synchronization must be maintained between LEDs to avoid time conflicts. Intermittent transmission of LEDs in the time domain can lead to a low data rate and decrease the positioning update rate [84].

4.2.4 Spatial Division Multiple Access

SDMA is mostly used in IS-based indoor positioning systems. LEDs distributed in different locations are captured in the FOV of the image sensor and imaged at different points on the image plane. As the position of the image sensor changes, the points corresponding to the LEDs on the image sensor are also changed. The distance between the image sensor and the individual LEDs can be obtained through geometric and trigonometric relationships.

5 Time-of-Flight Camera-based Visible Light Positioning Technology

Due to the rapid development of LED technology and its many advantages, LEDs have replaced the traditional incandescent lamps as the mainstream indoor lighting source. LED-based OWP systems are becoming increasingly attractive due to their dual function of illumination and communication. With the widespread usage of ToF cameras in mobile phones and other end devices, ToF cameras have transitioned from high-end professional products to consumer-level products. Accurate distance estimation between emitter and receiver is a prerequisite for accurate indoor positioning. Since distance estimation is the main function of ToF cameras, an indoor positioning technology based on ToF cameras and LEDs is very attractive.

In this chapter, we propose a visible light indoor positioning technology based on ToF cameras, analyze its feasibility, and explain the principles of the related positioning methods.

5.1 Overview of Our Positioning System

The model of visible light indoor positioning system based on ToF camera is depicted in Fig. 4.2. The complete process of VLP using arrays of ToF pixels is demonstrated in the workflow of Fig. 5.1. The whole process can be divided into three main modules: the transmitting module, the receiving module, and the positioning module.

The transmitter side of the system is composed of a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA), LED drivers, and NIR LEDs. We use the FPGA as a microcontroller to

Figure 5.1: The proposed workflow of OWP using arrays of ToF pixels.

generate the modulation control signals for five LEDs, but the FPGA can not directly drive the LEDs, due to their high current demand. The LED must have a corresponding driver. Note that the maximum modulation frequency of the LED will then be limited by the maximum modulation frequency of the driver. Therefore, the frequency modulation range of the LED should be taken into full account when the driver is designed or selected.

The principle of a common ToF camera is that the camera's illumination system emits modulated light signals, which are reflected by the scene and finally received by the camera's receiver. This operation model of the camera is also called active ToF camera. In visible light indoor positioning systems, the LEDs modulated by an FPGA are fixed on the ceiling as emitters, which substitute the illumination control system from the ToF camera and reduces the power consumption and potential safety risks. This camera is called a passive ToF camera [100].

The computer provides power and transfers data to the ToF camera via the USB cable. The ToF camera is configured to operate in multi-frequency acquisition mode, and the modulated signal is a 50% duty cycle square wave signal. However, the modulated light from the LEDs is usually considered to be sinusoidal. Therefore, the equivalent equations used to retrieve the amplitude and phase shift are still applicable when using square wave demodulated signals [101]. By measuring the number of accumulated electrons Q_i , $i \in (1, 2, 3, 4)$ generated from the photoelectric conversion in the corresponding sampling interval, as shown in Fig. 5.2. Eq. 2.8, Eq. 2.9 and Eq. 5.3 can be rewritten as:

$$A = \frac{\sqrt{(Q_3 - Q_1)^2 + (Q_4 - Q_2)^2}}{2} \quad (5.1)$$

$$\phi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{Q_4 - Q_2}{Q_3 - Q_1} \right) \quad (5.2)$$

Figure 5.2: The four phase sample process of an AMCW signal. C_1 to C_4 are control signals with 90° phase delay between each other.

$$B = \frac{Q_1 + Q_2 + Q_3 + Q_4}{4} \quad (5.3)$$

We use the FDMA multiplexing technique, in which five LEDs transmit five different frequencies of visible light signals, respectively. The ToF camera can distinguish the different light signals through cross-correlation against a periodic signal of matching frequency in the data acquisition process. After the individual acquisitions at different demodulation frequencies have been carried out, a complete frame of multi-frequency raw data becomes available. Using the “four phases” algorithm, the depth image and the amplitude image can be obtained for each demodulation frequency. The camera is in passive 3D mode, and most of the photons received by the ToF sensor come directly from the LED (LOS), so the amplitude image can be regarded as the radiation pattern of the LED at the pixel plane. The exact LED center point is identified by the radiation pattern on the amplitude image, and the distance between the camera and the LED can be determined in the depth image, where the most important step is to find the LED center point using a suitable distribution model. We used a Gaussian model to

approximate the radiation pattern of the LEDs on the amplitude image, and the location of the LED center on the image plane with sub-pixel resolution in the image plane can be localized. Since the location of the LED center on the image plane is not an integer, the estimated distance of the corresponding point on the depth image is obtained using the interpolation method. Due to the different positions of the LEDs, five different Gaussian models are used to determine the five different LED center point pixels, and then five relative distances are found from the depth images. Since the five LEDs are clock-synchronized, the TDOA algorithm is suitable for positioning. In addition, an AOA algorithm based on accurate knowledge of the lens normals for all ToF pixels can also be adopted. The normal vector corresponding to the pixel of the LED center point can be found out by the lens normal matrix, then the AOA can be calculated.

So far, we have obtained two independent estimates. Since least squares method is used in both AOA and TDOA localization algorithms, the extended least squares method combining AOA and TDOA can achieve more accurate positioning. In the following, we will discuss the amplitude distribution of LED based on Gaussian distribution, the AOA localization algorithm based on lens normal matrix, and the hybrid Chan/Taylor based TDOA localization algorithm.

5.2 Gaussian Approximation Model

The illuminance of light is the luminous flux per area. It tells the radiation power that falls onto a surface area. The LOS geometric model of an LED and a flat surface are shown in Fig. 5.3, where h is the vertical distance between the LED and the plane, r is the distance between the LED and the receiving point on the flat surface, d is the length of the projection of r on the plane, ϕ is the angle of incident light at the receiving point on the plane, which is equal to the angle of radiation from the LED to the receiving point, when the LED irradiates perpendicularly to the plane.

5.2.1 Illuminance Distribution

In general, the LED radiation pattern is assumed to follow the Lambertian radiation pattern. Eq. 4.4 gives the equation for the received power distribution. The equation for the illuminance distribution $f_L(d)$ with respect to the distance d is to given as [102]:

$$f_L(d) = \frac{m+1}{2\pi} f_0 \cos^{m+1}(\phi) \frac{1}{r^2} = \frac{(m+1)f_0}{2\pi h^2} \left(1 + \frac{d^2}{h^2}\right)^{-\frac{m+3}{2}} \quad (5.4)$$

where m is still the lambertian parameter [90] and f_0 is the total illuminance. When h is a constant, $f_L(d)$ depends mainly on d and m .

Figure 5.3: Schematic of a single LED illuminance pattern on the flat plane and LOS geometric model of the LED and receiving surface.

1D Illuminance Distribution with Gaussian Approximation Model

From Eq. 5.4, it can be found that $f_L(d)$ become larger as d increases. By taking the derivative of $f_L(d)$ with respect to d we get [102]:

$$f'_L(d) = \frac{(m+1)f_0}{2\pi h^2} \left(-\frac{m+3}{2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{d^2}{h^2}\right)^{-\frac{m+5}{2}} \frac{2d}{h^2} = -\frac{(m+3)d}{d^2 + h^2} f_L(d) \quad (5.5)$$

When ϕ is very small, i. e., when d is much smaller than h , $d^2 + h^2 \approx h^2$, so the derivative can be simplified as:

$$f'_L(d) \approx -\frac{(m+3)d}{h^2} f_L(d) \quad (5.6)$$

It can be observed that Eq. 5.6 is still a function of $f_L(d)$ after $f'_L(d)$ is derived, so we can assume that illuminance distribution conforms to the characteristics of an exponential function. The simplified $f'_L(d)$ satisfies the properties of Gaussian distribution. Therefore, we assume that a 1D Gaussian approximation model $f_G(d)$ exists, whose parameters can be derived by comparing it with $f_L(d)$. The 1D Gaussian approximation model is expressed as:

$$f_G(d) = \frac{C}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left\{-\frac{d^2}{2\sigma^2}\right\} \quad (5.7)$$

where, C is a coefficient and σ^2 is the variance. The derivative of $f_G(d)$ with respect to d is:

$$f'_G(d) = -\frac{d}{\sigma^2} f_G(d) \quad (5.8)$$

By comparing with Eq. 5.6, we get $\sigma^2 = \frac{h^2}{m+3}$. Then letting the Eq. 5.4 and Eq. 5.8 be equal at $d = 0$, we can obtain $C = \frac{(m+1)f_0}{h\sqrt{2\pi}\sqrt{m+3}}$. Therefore, we get

$$f_G(d) = \frac{(m+1)f_0}{2\pi h^2} \exp\left\{-\frac{m+3}{2h^2} \cdot d^2\right\} \quad (5.9)$$

Now we have obtained the illuminance distribution of the generalized Lambertian radiation pattern $f_L(d)$ and the illuminance distribution of the Gaussian model $f_G(d)$, respectively. Fig. 5.4 shows the illuminance distribution of the two models and the difference between them as a function of distance d at $h = 2.5$ m, and semi-angle at half power $\phi_{1/2} = 7.5^\circ$. It can be observed that the variation curve of illuminance distribution with distance d for the Gaussian approximation model is highly similar to that for the generalized Lambertian radiation pattern, and the error between them is small enough

to be negligible. At a distance greater than 0.857 m, the illuminance is so low that the human eye will not perceive the light, which corresponds to the normalized illuminance below -20 dB in Fig.5.4(b) [103].

Figure 5.4: The illuminance distribution (a) and the normalized illuminance distributions in dB (b) of the two models and the difference between them as a function of distance d at $h = 2.5$ m, and semi-angle at half power $\phi_{1/2} = 7.5^\circ$, which means $m = 40$.

2D Illuminance Distribution with Gaussian Approximation Model

It is feasible to approximate the illumination distribution of a generalized Lambertian model with a Gaussian model in the 1D case. In general, we analyze the illuminance distribution of the emitters in the 2D case, so the 1D illuminance distribution functions $f(d)$ are extended to the 2D case $f(x, y)$ by the relation $d^2 = x^2 + y^2$. $f_L(x, y)$ and $f_G(x, y)$ denote the 2D illuminance distribution under the Lambertian radiation pattern and under the Gaussian model, respectively. The 2D Fourier transform of $f_L(x, y)$ can be obtained as $F_L(u, v)$ [102]:

$$F_L(u, v) = \begin{cases} \frac{(-2)^{m/2} f_0 h^{m+1}}{(m-1)!!} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \right)^{m/2} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{\xi}} \exp(-2\pi\sqrt{\xi}\sqrt{u^2 + v^2}) \right] \Big|_{\xi=h^2} & \text{if } m \text{ is even} \\ \frac{(-2)^{(m+1)/2} f_0 h^{m+1}}{(m-1)!!} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \zeta} \right)^{(m+1)/2} \left[K_0(2\pi\sqrt{\zeta}\sqrt{u^2 + v^2}) \right] \Big|_{\zeta=h^2} & \text{if } m \text{ is odd} \end{cases} \quad (5.10)$$

where $m!!$ denotes the double factorial and $K_0(\cdot)$ is the modified Bessel function of the second kind [102].

The derivation of the two-dimensional Gaussian function and the derivation of the 2D Fourier transform are shown in Appendix A. The 2D Gaussian approximation function $f_G(x, y)$ is expressed as:

$$f_G(x, y) = \frac{C}{2\pi\sigma^2} \exp\left\{-\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2\sigma^2}\right\} \quad (5.11)$$

where C is a coefficient and σ^2 is the variance. After calculating, we get $\sigma^2 = \frac{h^2}{m+3}$, $C = \frac{(m+1)f_0}{m+3}$. Therefore, the two-dimensional Gaussian approximation equation is expressed as:

$$f_G(x, y) = \frac{(m+1)f_0}{2\pi h^2} \exp\left(-\frac{m+3}{2h^2}(x^2 + y^2)\right) \quad (5.12)$$

Since a Fourier transform of a Gaussian function is still a Gaussian function, the 2D Fourier transform of $f_G(x, y)$ can be obtained as $F_G(u, v)$ as:

$$F_G(u, v) = C \exp(-2\pi^2\sigma^2(u^2 + v^2)) = \frac{(m+1)f_0}{m+3} \exp\left(-\frac{2\pi^2 h^2}{m+3}(u^2 + v^2)\right) \quad (5.13)$$

From Fig. 5.5, we can observe that $F_L(u, v)$ and $F_G(u, v)$ are highly coincident, which means that in the 2D case the illuminance distribution based on the Lambertian radiation pattern can also be approximated by the Gaussian function.

5.2.2 Amplitude Distribution

Because illuminance is a measure of the intensity of illumination on a surface [104], the illuminance distribution can be understood as an amplitude distribution on an amplitude image when the array of ToF pixels is considered as the surface. Since the illuminance distribution with the Lambertian radiation pattern can be approximated by a Gaussian model, the amplitude distribution on the amplitude image can also be

Figure 5.5: The decibel values of the Fourier transforms as function of u and v , where the dotted line indicates $10 \log_{10} \frac{F_L(u,v)}{F_L(0,0)}$, and the solid line indicates $10 \log_{10} \frac{F_G(u,v)}{F_G(0,0)}$, when the LED is located at (1.5 m, 1.5 m, 2.5 m), and semi-angle at half power $\phi_{1/2} = 7.5^\circ$, which means $m = 40$.

approximated by a Gaussian model.

Maximum Likelihood Estimation

In general, the MLE is a method that uses observed data and a known probability distribution to estimate the parameters of the model which is most likely to match this observed data. An important prerequisite for MLE is that the observations from the sample $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N)$ are Independently and Identically Distributed (i.i.d.). The joint likelihood function can be written as:

$$L(\theta) = \mathcal{P}(X | \theta) = p(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N | \theta) = \prod_{i=1}^N p(x_i | \theta) \quad (5.14)$$

where θ are the model parameters. MLE is aimed at finding the values of the model parameters θ that maximize the likelihood function [105], that is:

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \max_{\theta} L(\theta) = \arg \max_{\theta} \prod_{i=1}^N p(x_i | \theta) \quad (5.15)$$

In practice, it is defined as a log-likelihood function for analytical purposes:

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \max_{\theta} \log L(\theta) = \arg \max_{\theta} \log \prod_{i=1}^N p(x_i | \theta) \quad (5.16)$$

In the case of univariate Gaussian distribution, we can know that:

$$x_i \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2), \theta = (\mu, \sigma^2)$$

$$p(x_i | \theta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{(x_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (5.17)$$

Substituting the Eq. 5.17 into Eq. 5.16, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\theta} &= \arg \max_{\theta} \log \prod_{i=1}^N p(x_i | \theta) \\ &= \arg \max_{\theta} \sum_{i=1}^N \log p(x_i | \theta) \\ &= \arg \max_{\theta} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{(x_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \\ &= \arg \max_{\theta} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\log \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} + \log \frac{1}{\sigma} - \frac{(x_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.18)$$

For the mean μ_{MLE} :

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{\text{MLE}} &= \arg \max_{\mu} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(-\frac{(x_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) \\ &= \arg \min_{\mu} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{(x_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) \\ &= \arg \min_{\mu} \sum_{i=1}^N ((x_i - \mu)^2) \end{aligned} \quad (5.19)$$

Letting $\frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2 = 0$, we can get:

$$\mu_{\text{MLE}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i \quad (5.20)$$

Similarly, for the variance σ_{MLE} :

$$\sigma_{\text{MLE}} = \arg \max_{\sigma} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(-\log \sigma - \frac{(x_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) \quad (5.21)$$

Solving the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \sigma} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(-\log \sigma - \frac{(x_i - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) = 0 \quad (5.22)$$

We obtain:

$$\sigma_{\text{MLE}}^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu_{\text{MLE}})^2 \quad (5.23)$$

In the case of multivariate Gaussian distribution with the mean μ and the variance Σ , the parameter Θ are as follows:

$$\mu_{\text{MLE}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{p}_i \quad (5.24)$$

and

$$\Sigma_{\text{MLE}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\mathbf{p}_i - \mu_{\text{MLE}}) (\mathbf{p}_i - \mu_{\text{MLE}})^T \quad (5.25)$$

In amplitude images, the matrix \mathbf{p}_i contains the coordinates of all the pixel points occupied by the LED in the image plane. Considering the matrix \mathbf{p}_i as the observed sample matrix, the model parameters μ_{MLE} and Σ_{MLE} of the 2D Gaussian distribution can be calculated by Eq. 5.24 and Eq. 5.25, respectively, where μ_{MLE} is the coordinate of the LED center point in the image plane.

So far, we have discussed models with a single LED or an LED module that can be considered as a single LED. However, in practice, a single LED is rarely used, and LED

modules consisting of multiple LEDs are the most common. The contours of the illuminance distribution of the different LED modules are shown in Fig. 5.6. In Fig. 5.6(a) a single LED is used as the light source. In Fig. 5.6(b), the LED module comprises nine closely-arranged LEDs, and their illuminance distribution can be equivalent to the illuminance distribution from a single LED (like in Fig. 5.6(a)). When the LED module consists of two separated LEDs, as shown in Fig. 5.6(c), the contour lines of the illuminance distribution are separated from each other (no overlap). When the LED module is composed of 4 LEDs, it is observed in Fig. 5.6(d) that the contour lines of the illuminance distribution may overlap with each other. For the cases presented in Fig. 5.6(c) and Fig. 5.6(d), the single model estimation is invalid, but using a mixture model can more accurately match the real scenario.

Figure 5.6: Schematic diagram of the radiation model of different LED modules and the contour lines of the illuminance distribution on the image plane.

Gaussian Mixture Model

A Gaussian mixture model can be regarded as a combination of K single Gaussian models. If the observations are denoted as X_i , the probability distribution function can be written as:

$$\mathcal{P}(X_i = x) = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{P}(X_i = x \mid Z_i = k) \quad (5.26)$$

where Z_i is a latent variable, $P(X_i | Z_i)$ is the probability density function of Gaussian distribution shortened as $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma)$ and π_k denotes the probability that X_i belongs to k -th component, with $\pi_k \geq 0$, $\sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k = 1$.

In the case of Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM), the joint likelihood function Eq. 5.14 can be rewritten as:

$$L(\theta | X_1, \dots, X_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{N}(x_i; \mu_k, \Sigma_k) \quad (5.27)$$

where $\theta = (\pi_k, \mu_k, \Sigma_k)$, $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, K$, are set of unknown parameters of the GMM. Similarly, the log-likelihood function is :

$$\ell(\theta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left(\sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{N}(x_i; \mu_k, \Sigma_k) \right) \quad (5.28)$$

We can not use the MLE method to derive the parameter that maximizes the likelihood as in the single Gaussian model, because we do not know from which Gaussian mixture component each sample is generated. In this case, we usually use the EM algorithm to find the maximum likelihood of the model through iterations [106].

The EM algorithm is made of the following steps [107]:

1. **Initialization:** Given the initialization parameters μ_k^0 , Σ_k^0 and π_k^0 .
2. **E-step:** Calculate the posterior probabilities $\gamma_{Z_i}(k)$ using the current values of the parameters.

The posterior probability is expressed as:

$$\gamma_{Z_i}(k) = \frac{\pi_k \mathcal{N}(x_i; \mu_k, \Sigma_k)}{\sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{N}(x_i; \mu_k, \Sigma_k)} \quad (5.29)$$

3. **M-step:** Calculate the new μ_k^{new} , Σ_k^{new} and π_k^{new} . Since we have obtained $\gamma_{Z_i}(k)$ in **E-step**, the dataset is now complete and the MLE can be used to solve for the

parameters. We take the first-order partial derivatives of the log-likelihood $\ell(\theta)$ with respect to μ_k , σ_k and π_k respectively, and set the obtained expressions equal to zero and solve them as follows [107]:

$$\mu_k^{new} = \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_{z_i}(k) x_i \quad (5.30)$$

$$\Sigma_k^{new} = \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_{z_i}(k) (x_i - \mu_k^{new}) (x_i - \mu_k^{new})^T \quad (5.31)$$

$$\pi_k^{new} = \frac{N_k}{n} \quad (5.32)$$

where $N_k = \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_{z_i}(k)$

4. **Iteration:** Calculate the log-likelihood $\ell(\theta^{i+1})$ with the new parameters. If $|\ell(\theta^{i+1}) - \ell(\theta^i)| \leq \varepsilon$, stop. Otherwise, go back to step 2.

5.3 Angle of Arrival Algorithm Based on Lens Normal Matrix

For accurate indoor positioning with ToF cameras, camera calibration is an important and indispensable part. When the camera lens is calibrated, we can obtain the matrix of lens normals. Since the matrix of lens normals contains the observed direction of each pixel, when the location of the pixel is known, it also means that the angle of the light arriving at the pixel is known. The AOA algorithm based on the lens normal matrix can be divided into two parts, one is to combine the amplitude image and the lens normal matrix to solve for the AOA, and the other part is to use the obtained AOA for positioning, as shown in the Fig. 5.7.

Figure 5.7: Flowchart of the AOA algorithm based on accurate knowledge of the lens normals for all ToF pixels.

Figure 5.8: Image plane. The purple arrow is the component of the matrix of lens normals on the image plane at the location of the LED center.

The size of the lens normal matrix is $n_{\text{rows}} \times n_{\text{cols}} \times 3$, where $n_{\text{rows}} \times n_{\text{cols}}$ indicates the size of the array of ToF pixels. The light emitted from the LED are collected by the lens and finally received by the array of ToF pixels. The pixel coordinates of the LED center point can be calculated by either using the MLE in a single Gaussian model or the EM method in GMM. Once we have obtained the pixel coordinates of the LED center-point in the image plane, we can retrieve the normal vector of the corresponding pixel point from the lens normal matrix. Fig. 5.8 shows an example of the location of an LED on the image plane. n_x and n_y are the components of the unit normal at the location of the LED center-point on the X_i and Y_i axes, respectively.

The AOA Includes azimuth angle and elevation angle. In Fig. 4.7 and Fig. 5.8, ϕ indicates the azimuth angle. azimuth angle ψ shons in Fig. 4.7. When we consider only the 2D case, AOA is the azimuth angle on the image plane, which can be derived by n_x and n_y . The expression is as follows:

$$\tan \phi_i = \frac{n_{yi}}{n_{xi}}, i \in (1, 2, 3, \dots, m) \quad (5.33)$$

where the m is the number of LEDs. We substitute the calculated ϕ_i into Eq. 4.15, Eq. 4.16, and use the least-squares method to find the position of the ToF camera.

5.4 The Hybrid Chan/Taylor-Based Time Difference of Arrival Localization Algorithm

Assume that the relative height difference between the robot with ToF camera and the ceiling is constant so that the whole scene can be considered as in a 2D plane, as shown in Fig. 5.9. There are M clock-synchronized LEDs installed on the ceiling and they are at the locations $(x_i, y_i), i = 1, 2, \dots, M$. The unknown coordinates of the center of the ToF camera (x, y) . According to the geometric relationships between LEDs and ToF camera, we can obtain the equation of the distance from LED to ToF camera, which is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} r_i^2 &= (x_i - x)^2 + (y_i - y)^2 \\ &= K_i - 2x_i x + 2y_i y + x^2 + y^2 \end{aligned} \quad (5.34)$$

where K_i is a known constant:

$$K_i = x_i^2 + y_i^2$$

Figure 5.9: Geometric relationship between LEDs and ToF camera in a 2D plane.

The distance difference $r_{i,1}$ between the ToF camera to the i -th LED and the 1st LED is:

$$r_{i,1} = r_i - r_1 = \sqrt{(x_i - x)^2 + (y_i - y)^2} - \sqrt{(x_1 - x)^2 + (y_1 - y)^2} \quad (5.35)$$

Bringing Eq. 5.35 into Eq. 5.34, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} (r_{i,1} + r_1)^2 &= K_i - 2x_i x - 2y_i y + x^2 + y^2 \\ r_{i,1}^2 + 2r_{i,1}r_1 + r_1^2 &= K_i - 2x_i x - 2y_i y + x^2 + y^2 \\ r_{i,1}^2 + 2r_{i,1}r_1 + (x_1 - x)^2 + (y_1 - y)^2 &= K_i - 2x_i x - 2y_i y + x^2 + y^2 \\ r_{i,1}^2 + 2r_{i,1}r_1 &= K_i - 2x_i x - 2y_i y + 2x_1 x + 2y_1 y - (x_1^2 + y_1^2) \\ r_{i,1}^2 + 2r_{i,1}r_1 &= K_i - K_1 - 2(x_i - x_1)x - 2(y_i - y_1)y \\ r_{i,1}^2 + 2r_{i,1}r_1 &= (K_i - K_1) - 2x_{i,1}x - 2y_{i,1}y \end{aligned} \quad (5.36)$$

where,

$$x_{i,1} = x_i - x_1, y_{i,1} = y_i - y_1$$

.

5.4.1 Chan's Method

The Chan method [108] is based on a non-recursive hyperbolic equation system with analytic expression solutions. Its main features are its high localization accuracy and low calculation when the measurement error obeys the ideal Gaussian distribution. The accuracy of the method can be improved by increasing the number of base stations (LEDs).

When $M = 3$, the number of unknowns is equal to the number of equations. The

Eq. 5.36 can be written as:

$$\begin{cases} r_{2,1}^2 + 2r_{2,1}r_1 = (K_2 - K_1) - 2x_{2,1}x - 2y_{2,1}y \\ r_{3,1}^2 + 2r_{3,1}r_1 = (K_3 - K_1) - 2x_{3,1}x - 2y_{3,1}y \end{cases} \quad (5.37)$$

which is written in matrix format as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{2,1} & y_{2,1} \\ x_{3,1} & y_{3,1} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}(K_2 - K_1 - r_{2,1}^2) - r_{2,1}r_1 \\ \frac{1}{2}(K_3 - K_1 - r_{3,1}^2) - r_{3,1}r_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.38)$$

The solution of x and y with respect to r_1 can be brought into Eq. 5.34 to obtain a quadratic equation with respect to r_1 , and the valid root can be brought back to the Eq. 5.38 to find the estimated position of the ToF camera.

When the number of LEDs is greater than 3, the number of nonlinear equations is more than the number of unknowns. By using the Weighted Least Squares (WLS) method to make full use of the redundant data, the Chan algorithm can obtain a better estimation of the ToF camera. In this case, the initial nonlinear TDOA equations are first converted into linear equations, then the initial solution is obtained using WLS. A second WLS estimation is performed using the first obtained estimated position and known constraints to obtain the improved position estimate.

We first assume that x , y and r_1 are mutually independent variables, then the pseudo-linear equations can be written in the following form:

$$\mathbf{G}_0 \mathbf{z}_0 = \mathbf{h}_0 \quad (5.39)$$

where

$$\mathbf{G}_0 = - \begin{bmatrix} x_{2,1} & y_{2,1} & r_{2,1} \\ x_{3,1} & y_{3,1} & r_{3,1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_{M,1} & y_{M,1} & r_{M,1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.40)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_0 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} r_{2,1}^2 - K_2 + K_1 \\ r_{3,1}^2 - K_3 + K_1 \\ \vdots \\ r_{M,1}^2 - K_M + K_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.41)$$

$\mathbf{z}_0 = [\mathbf{P}_0, r_1]^\top$ is the unknown vector, where $\mathbf{P}_0 = [x, y]^\top$.

In practice, considering the existence of signal noise, there is also a certain error in the time difference estimation. Therefore, the actual time difference estimation is

$$\hat{d}_{i,1} = d_{i,1} + n_{i,1} \quad (5.42)$$

where $n_{i,1}$ denotes the error of the time difference estimation, and let:

$$\mathbf{n} = [n_{2,1}, n_{3,1}, \dots, n_{M,1}]^\top \quad (5.43)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{d}} = [\hat{d}_{2,1}, \hat{d}_{3,1}, \dots, \hat{d}_{M,1}]^\top \quad (5.44)$$

The mean value of the error of the time difference estimation is $\mathbf{0}$. The covariance matrix

\mathbf{Q} of the time difference estimation is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{Q} &= \mathbb{E} \left\{ (\hat{\mathbf{d}} - \mathbb{E}\{\hat{\mathbf{d}}\})(\hat{\mathbf{d}} - \mathbb{E}\{\hat{\mathbf{d}}\})^\top \right\} \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left\{ (\hat{\mathbf{d}} - \mathbf{d})(\hat{\mathbf{d}} - \mathbf{d})^\top \right\} \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left\{ \mathbf{nn}^\top \right\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.45}$$

The error in the distance estimation due to the error of time difference can be expressed as:

$$r_{i,1}^{\hat{}} = r_{i,1} + cn_{i,1} \tag{5.46}$$

where c is the speed of light. Because of the effect of errors, the real \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{h} are:

$$\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{G}_0 + \Delta\mathbf{G} = - \begin{bmatrix} x_{2,1} & y_{2,1} & \hat{r}_{2,1} \\ x_{3,1} & y_{3,1} & \hat{r}_{3,1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_{M,1} & y_{M,1} & \hat{r}_{M,1} \end{bmatrix} \tag{5.47}$$

$$\mathbf{h} = \mathbf{h}_0 + \Delta\mathbf{h} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{r}_{2,1}^2 - K_2 + K_1 \\ \hat{r}_{3,1}^2 - K_3 + K_1 \\ \vdots \\ \hat{r}_{M,1}^2 - K_M + K_1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{5.48}$$

where

$$\Delta\mathbf{G} = - \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & cn_{2,1} \\ 0 & 0 & cn_{3,1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & cn_{M,1} \end{bmatrix} \tag{5.49}$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{h} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 2cr_{2,1}n_{2,1} + c^2n_{2,1}^2 \\ 2cr_{3,1}n_{3,1} + c^2n_{3,1}^2 \\ \vdots \\ 2cr_{M,1}n_{M,1} + c^2n_{M,1}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.50)$$

In the presence of errors, the error vector from Eq. 5.39 is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\varphi} &= \mathbf{h} - \mathbf{G}\mathbf{z}_0 \\ &= \mathbf{h}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{h} - (\mathbf{G}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{G})\mathbf{z}_0 \\ &= \Delta \mathbf{h} - \Delta \mathbf{G}\mathbf{z}_0 \end{aligned} \quad (5.51)$$

Substituting Eq. 5.49 and Eq. 5.50 into Eq. 5.51, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\varphi} &= \Delta \mathbf{h} - \Delta \mathbf{G}\mathbf{z}_0 \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 2cr_{2,1}n_{2,1} + c^2n_{2,1}^2 \\ 2cr_{3,1}n_{3,1} + c^2n_{3,1}^2 \\ \vdots \\ 2cr_{M,1}n_{M,1} + c^2n_{M,1}^2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} cr_1n_{2,1} \\ cr_1n_{3,1} \\ \vdots \\ cr_1n_{M,1} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} cr_2n_{2,1} + \frac{1}{2}c^2n_{2,1}^2 \\ cr_3n_{3,1} + \frac{1}{2}c^2n_{3,1}^2 \\ \vdots \\ cr_Mn_{M,1} + \frac{1}{2}c^2n_{M,1}^2 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= c\mathbf{B}\mathbf{n} + \frac{1}{2}c^2\mathbf{n} \odot \mathbf{n} \end{aligned} \quad (5.52)$$

where \odot denotes Hadamard product, $\mathbf{B} = \text{diag}(r_2, r_3, \dots, r_M)$. In the general case, $cn_{i,1} \ll r_i$ is often met and the second term on the right side of the Eq. 5.52 can be ignored. Therefore the errors $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ can be regarded as zero-mean Gaussian random vectors, which

have a covariance matrix as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{\Psi} &= \text{E} \{ \boldsymbol{\varphi} \boldsymbol{\varphi}^\top \} \\
 &= c^2 \text{E} \{ \mathbf{B} \mathbf{n} \mathbf{n}^\top \mathbf{B}^\top \} \\
 &= c^2 \mathbf{B} \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{B}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.53}$$

To obtain more accurate target location estimation, we perform two step WLS, the first WLS to obtain the initial target location estimation, and the second WLS to find the final position estimation using the relationship between the target (ToF camera) and the base station (LED) (e.g., Eq. 5.34 at $i = 1$).

The First Step WLS

Assume that x, y, r_1 are mutually independent variables. Using the WLS to solve Eq. 5.51, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{\mathbf{z}}_0 &= \text{argmin} (\mathbf{h} - \mathbf{G} \mathbf{z}_0)^\top \mathbf{\Psi}^{-1} (\mathbf{h} - \mathbf{G} \mathbf{z}_0) \\
 &= (\mathbf{G}^\top \mathbf{\Psi}^{-1} \mathbf{G})^{-1} \mathbf{G}^\top \mathbf{\Psi}^{-1} \mathbf{h}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.54}$$

Since the actual distance from the target to the base station is unknown, the unknown \mathbf{B} also leads to the unknown $\mathbf{\Psi}$.

When the receivers are all far from the transmitters, the distance from the receiver to each transmitter can be initially approximated as equal, i.e., $r_i \approx r_1$. Therefore, we have:

$$\mathbf{B} \approx r_1 \mathbf{I} \tag{5.55}$$

where \mathbf{I} is the unit matrix. So that:

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}}_0 = (\mathbf{G}^\top \mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{G})^{-1} \mathbf{G}^\top \mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{h} \tag{5.56}$$

When the distance is close, an initial result can be obtained by using Eq. 5.56 to estimate

\mathbf{B} and Ψ . Substituting Ψ into Eq. 5.54, the first-step WLS estimation of the target position can be obtained.

The Second Step WLS

In fact, x, y, r_1 have the relationship: $r_1^2 = (x_1 - x)^2 + (y_1 - y)^2$. A certain error is caused by approximating Ψ with \mathbf{Q} . For a more accurate localization result, a second WLS estimation can be followed.

The $\hat{\mathbf{z}}_0$ is expressed in the following form:

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{z}}_o(1) \\ \hat{\mathbf{z}}_o(2) \\ \hat{\mathbf{z}}_o(3) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x + \Delta x \\ y + \Delta y \\ r_1 + \Delta r_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.57)$$

where $\Delta x, \Delta y$ and Δr_1 are estimation errors of \mathbf{z}_0 . The first two elements of the Eq. 5.57 are subtracted by x_1 and y_1 , respectively, and squaring the three elements yields:

$$\mathbf{h}' - \mathbf{G}'\mathbf{z}' = \varphi' \quad (5.58)$$

where

$$\mathbf{h}' = \begin{bmatrix} (\hat{\mathbf{z}}_0(1) - x_1)^2 \\ (\hat{\mathbf{z}}_0(2) - y_1)^2 \\ \hat{\mathbf{z}}_0^2(3) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.59)$$

$$\mathbf{G}' = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.60)$$

$$\mathbf{z}' = \begin{bmatrix} (x - x_1)^2 \\ (y - y_1)^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.61)$$

Substituting Eq. 5.57 into Eq. 5.59 gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi'(1) &= 2(x - x_1) \Delta x + \Delta^2 x \approx 2(x - x_1) \Delta x \\ \varphi'(2) &= 2(y - y_1) \Delta y + \Delta^2 y \approx 2(y - y_1) \Delta y \\ \varphi'(3) &= 2r_1 \Delta r_1 + \Delta^2 r_1 \approx 2r_1 \Delta r_1 \end{aligned} \quad (5.62)$$

namely:

$$\varphi' \approx 2[(x - x_1) \Delta x, (y - y_1) \Delta y, r_1 \Delta r_1]^\top = 2\mathbf{B}' \Delta \mathbf{z} \quad (5.63)$$

where $\mathbf{B}' = \text{diag}((x - x_1), (y - y_1), r_1)$.

The covariance matrix of the error φ' is:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi' &= \mathbb{E} \left\{ (\varphi' - \mathbb{E} \{\varphi'\}) (\{\varphi'\} - \mathbb{E} \{\varphi'\})^\top \right\} \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left\{ \varphi' \varphi'^T \right\} \\ &= 4 \begin{bmatrix} (x - x_1)^2 \mathbb{E} \{\Delta^2 x\} & (x - x_1)(y - y_1) \mathbb{E} \{\Delta x \Delta y\} & (x - x_1) r_1 \mathbb{E} \{\Delta x \Delta r_1\} \\ (x - x_1)(y - y_1) \mathbb{E} \{\Delta x \Delta y\} & (y - y_1)^2 \mathbb{E} \{\Delta^2 y\} & (y - y_1) r_1 \mathbb{E} \{\Delta y \Delta r_1\} \\ (x - x_1) r_1 \mathbb{E} \{\Delta x \Delta r_1\} & (y - y_1) r_1 \mathbb{E} \{\Delta y \Delta r_1\} & r_1^2 \mathbb{E} \{\Delta^2 r_1\} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= 4\mathbf{B}' \text{cov}(\hat{\mathbf{z}}_0) \mathbf{B}' \end{aligned} \quad (5.64)$$

Both sides of the Eq. 5.54 are left multiplied by $\mathbf{G}^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}$, which gives,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\mathbf{G}^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}) \hat{\mathbf{z}}_0 &= \mathbf{G}^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{h} \\
 (\mathbf{G}_0^\top + \Delta \mathbf{G}^\top) \Psi^{-1} (\mathbf{G}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{G}) (\mathbf{z}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{z}) &= (\mathbf{G}_0^\top + \Delta \mathbf{G}^\top) \Psi^{-1} (\mathbf{h}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{h}) \\
 (\mathbf{G}_0^\top + \Delta \mathbf{G}^\top) \Psi^{-1} (\mathbf{G}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{G}) \Delta \mathbf{z} &= (\mathbf{G}_0^\top + \Delta \mathbf{G}^\top) \Psi^{-1} (\mathbf{h}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{h} - \mathbf{G}_0 \mathbf{z}_0 - \Delta \mathbf{G} \mathbf{z}_0) \\
 (\mathbf{G}_0^\top + \Delta \mathbf{G}^\top) \Psi^{-1} (\mathbf{G}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{G}) \Delta \mathbf{z} &\approx (\mathbf{G}_0^\top + \Delta \mathbf{G}^\top) \Psi^{-1} \boldsymbol{\varphi}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.65}$$

Retaining the first-order perturbation components and omitting the higher-order perturbations, and then bringing the Eq. 5.52 to Eq. 5.65, $\Delta \mathbf{z}$ is given by:

$$\Delta \mathbf{z} = c (\mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0)^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{n} \tag{5.66}$$

Using Eq. 5.53, the covariance matrix of $\hat{\mathbf{z}}_0$ is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{cov}(\hat{\mathbf{z}}_0) &= \text{E} \{ \Delta \mathbf{z} \Delta \mathbf{z}^\top \} \\
 &= \text{E} \left\{ c^2 (\mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0)^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{n} \mathbf{n}^\top \mathbf{B} \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0 (\mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0)^{-1} \right\} \\
 &= c^2 (\mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0)^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{B} \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0 (\mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0)^{-1} \\
 &= (\mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0)^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0 (\mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0)^{-1} \\
 &= (\mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0)^{-1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.67}$$

Therefore, the covariance Ψ of the error $\boldsymbol{\varphi}'$ is transformed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi' &= 4 \mathbf{B}' \text{cov}(\hat{\mathbf{z}}_0) \mathbf{B}' \\
 &= 4 \mathbf{B}' (\mathbf{G}_0^\top \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0)^{-1} \mathbf{B}'
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.68}$$

Similarly, the WLS solution for $\hat{\mathbf{z}}'$ is:

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}}' = (\mathbf{G}'^\top \Psi'^{-1} \mathbf{G}')^{-1} \mathbf{G}'^\top \Psi'^{-1} \mathbf{h}' \tag{5.69}$$

Finally, the target position is estimated as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \pm\sqrt{\hat{\mathbf{z}}'(1)} \\ \pm\sqrt{\hat{\mathbf{z}}'(2)} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ y_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.70)$$

This algorithm can make full use of the information from each base station, which can effectively reduce the negative impact of large measurement errors of single base stations on positioning.

5.4.2 Taylor Series Expansion Method

The Taylor series expansion method is an iterative algorithm. The premise of the Taylor series expansion algorithm is that an initial estimation of the target's position is required, and the main idea of the algorithm is to correct the estimation of the target by iterating continuously. Finally, the real position is approximated gradually.

The constrained relationship between the target and base station can be expressed by a certain function $f_i(x, y, x_i, y_i)$, whose measured value can be represented by $M_i(x, y, x_i, y_i)$, with $M_i = M_i^0 + e_i$, where $M_i^0(x_0, y_0, x_i, y_i)$ is the actual value, $e_i(\Delta x + \Delta y)$ represents the measurement error. η is the error threshold value. Then, the iterative computation should be stopped when the condition: $|\Delta x| + |\Delta y| < \eta$ is satisfied.

Assume that the initial value of the target coordinates is (x_0, y_0) . The true values are (x, y) with $x = x_0 + \Delta x$, $y = y_0 + \Delta y$. Then the Taylor series expansion of the function $f_i(x, y, x_i, y_i)$ at (x_0, y_0) results in the following:

$$\begin{aligned} f_i(x, y, x_i, y_i) &= f_i(x_0, y_0, x_i, y_i) + \left(\Delta x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \Delta y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) f_i(x_0, y_0, x_i, y_i) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\Delta x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \Delta y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right)^2 f_i(x_0, y_0, x_i, y_i) + \cdots \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{n!} \left(\Delta x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \Delta y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right)^n f_i(x_0, y_0, x_i, y_i) + \cdots \end{aligned} \quad (5.71)$$

Based on the geometric relationship between the target and the base station, when

$j = 1$ is chosen as the reference point, the function $f_i(x, y, x_i, y_i)$ is constructed as:

$$\begin{aligned} f_i(x, y, x_i, y_i) &= c(t_i - t_j) = r_i - r_j \\ &= \sqrt{(x_i - x)^2 + (y_i - y)^2} - \sqrt{(x_j - x)^2 + (y_j - y)^2}, j = 1, i = (2, 3, \dots, M) \end{aligned} \quad (5.72)$$

In different functions M_i, M_i^0 , and e_i have different meanings. In this case, M_i are $r_{i,1}$, $i \neq 1$, M_i^0 are $(r_i - r_1)$, $i \neq 1$, and e_i means errors. Taking the Taylor expansion of $f_i(x, y, x_i, y_i)$ at (x_0, y_0) and neglecting the components above the second order and transforming it into matrix form, we have:

$$\psi = \mathbf{h}_{\mathbf{t}_i} - \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{t}_i} \delta \quad (5.73)$$

where ψ is error vector,

$$\mathbf{h}_{\mathbf{t}_i} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{2,1} - (r_2 - r_1) \\ r_{3,1} - (r_3 - r_1) \\ \vdots \\ r_{M,1} - (r_M - r_1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.74)$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{t}_i} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{x_1 - x_0}{r_1} - \frac{x_2 - x_0}{r_2} & \frac{y_1 - y_0}{r_1} - \frac{y_2 - y_0}{r_2} \\ \frac{x_1 - x_0}{r_1} - \frac{x_3 - x_0}{r_3} & \frac{y_1 - y_0}{r_1} - \frac{y_3 - y_0}{r_3} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{x_1 - x_0}{r_1} - \frac{x_M - x_0}{r_M} & \frac{y_1 - y_0}{r_1} - \frac{y_M - y_0}{r_M} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.75)$$

$$\delta = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x \\ \Delta y \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.76)$$

The least squares solution for Eq. 5.73 is:

$$\delta = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x \\ \Delta y \end{bmatrix} = (\mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{t}_i}^\top \mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{t}_i})^{-1} \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{t}_i}^\top \mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{h}_{\mathbf{t}_i} \quad (5.77)$$

In the next iteration, $x_0 + \Delta x, y_0 + \Delta y$ will be operated instead of the original x_0 and y_0 . Continuing the above process until Δx and Δy are sufficiently small to satisfy the iteration stopping condition, and the position estimation of the unknown target can be obtained as: $(x_0 + \Delta x, y_0 + \Delta y)^T$.

The accuracy of Taylor series expansion method of localization is strongly related to the choice of initial values. With a good selection of the initial target position, the localization accuracy of the Taylor series expansions method is high and the algorithm converges quickly. If the initial target location is poorly selected, the algorithm is computationally intensive, tends to fall into local minima, and convergence is difficult to guarantee [108].

The localization results obtained by the Chan method are already highly accurate, and if the localization results from the Chan method are used as the initial values for Taylor series expansion method again, the accuracy of the final results will be further improved.

5.5 Fusion algorithm for Angle of Arrival/Time Difference of Arrival

We have introduced the indoor localization using the AOA algorithm leveraging knowledge of the lens normals of the ToF camera in Sec. 5.3 and the TDOA algorithm with the hybrid Chan/Taylor method in Sec. 5.4.2. Fusing the two algorithms to achieve more accurate localization is also to be considered.

Fig. 5.10 shows the linear approximation of the AOA algorithm, where the Base Station (BS) is used as the coordinate origin. According to Fig. 5.10, we can derive the AOA equation as:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y - y_1}{x - x_1} \right) + \theta' \quad (5.78)$$

Figure 5.10: Linear approximation of AOA algorithm from reference [7].

where (x, y) is the location of Mobile Station (MS), (x_1, y_1) is the location of BS, θ is the measure angle between BS (LED) and MS (ToF camera), and θ' is the error angle. From the triangulation on Fig. 5.10, we can get [7]:

$$D \sin \theta' = x \sin \theta - y \cos \theta \quad (5.79)$$

where D is the distance between BS and MS.

When $|\theta'| \ll 1$, the function $\sin \theta'$ can be approximated as θ' . Therefore, the Eq. 5.79 can be simplified as [7]:

$$D\theta' = x \sin \theta - y \cos \theta \quad (5.80)$$

From the Eq. 5.80, we can construct the function as:

$$\theta = g_i(x, y, x_i, y_i) = x \sin \left(\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y - y_i}{x - x_i} \right) \right) - y \cos \left(\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y - y_i}{x - x_i} \right) \right), \quad (5.81)$$

$$i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M$$

where M is the number of BS in the whole system. Similar to Sec. 5.4.2, assume that the initial value of MS coordinates is (x_0, y_0) . The true values are (x, y) with $x = x_0 + \Delta x$,

$y = y_0 + \Delta y$. Then the Taylor series expansion of the function $g_i(x, y, x_i, y_i)$ at (x_0, y_0) results in the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_i &= g_i(x_0, y_0, x_i, y_i) \\ &= g_i(x_0, y_0, x_i, y_i) + \left(\Delta x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \Delta y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) g_i(x_0, y_0, x_i, y_i) + \dots \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{n!} \left(\Delta x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \Delta y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right)^n g_i(x_0, y_0, x_i, y_i) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (5.82)$$

θ_i represents the angle between MS and each BS. When the initial position is given, θ_i can be obtained using the knowledge of the matrix of lens normals of the camera. Therefore, when omitting the components above the second order and transforming into a matrix form, we obtain:

$$\psi = \mathbf{h}_{\mathbf{a}i} - \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{a}i} \delta \quad (5.83)$$

where ψ is error vector,

$$\mathbf{h}_{\mathbf{a}i} = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_1 - g_1(x_0, y_0, x_1, y_1) \\ \theta_2 - g_2(x_0, y_0, x_2, y_2) \\ \vdots \\ \theta_M - g_M(x_0, y_0, x_M, y_M) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.84)$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{a}i} = \begin{bmatrix} \left. \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial x} \right|_{x=x_0, y=y_0} & \left. \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial y} \right|_{x=x_0, y=y_0} \\ \left. \frac{\partial g_2}{\partial x} \right|_{x=x_0, y=y_0} & \left. \frac{\partial g_2}{\partial y} \right|_{x=x_0, y=y_0} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \left. \frac{\partial g_M}{\partial x} \right|_{x=x_0, y=y_0} & \left. \frac{\partial g_M}{\partial y} \right|_{x=x_0, y=y_0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.85)$$

$$\delta = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x \\ \Delta y \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.86)$$

When the AOA algorithm and the hybrid Chan/Taylor method use the same initial

values, combining Eq. 5.75, Eq. 5.74, Eq. 5.85, and Eq. 5.84, the matrix form of the combined AOA and TDOA algorithms is represented as:

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{A}\delta \quad (5.87)$$

where

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{h}_{\mathbf{t}i} \\ \mathbf{h}_{\mathbf{a}i} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.88)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{t}i} \\ \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{a}i} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.89)$$

δ can be obtained via the least squares method as:

$$\delta = (\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{Y} \quad (5.90)$$

We argue that using the extended least squares method to fuzz the AOA algorithm and the TDOA algorithm, the accuracy of localization can be higher than just with a single localization method.

6 Simulations and Tests

In the previous chapter, we detailed the theory of indoor visible light localization based on arrays of ToF pixels. We showed feasibility of the transition from theory to practice by discussing the key techniques. In this chapter, we will validate our proposed scheme through simulations and experiments in the laboratory. Following the experimental setup in Fig. 4.2, we need to use a set of orthogonal frequencies to modulate the five LED modules fixed in the ceiling. The ToF camera as a receiver on a plane located 2.5 m below the ceiling.

6.1 Experimental Scenarios and Equipments

6.1.1 Experimental Scenarios

In order to simulate and test our proposed positioning system, we designed an experimental setup according to Fig. 4.2. An LED module frame with a size of $2\text{ m} \times 2\text{ m}$ was built and planned to be fixed to the ceiling. Four LED modules were placed at the four corners, and one LED module was placed at the center. An FPGA was also needed as a modulation signal generator. The receiver was fixed on a plane at a distance of 2 m from the ceiling. The FPGA and a power bank which supplies power to the FPGA were also placed in the center of the LED frame. The FPGA allows five LEDs to be modulated at five different frequencies simultaneously. In order to ensure that each LED module works under the same conditions, the length of the power cable, the length of the signal cable and the specifications of the various connectors are all guaranteed to be the same. For the convenience of the experiment, we did not mount the LED frame on the ceiling.

Instead, we fixed the LED frame on one wall, as shown in Fig. 6.1(a). Since the LED module is composed of two LEDs, we assume that the midpoint between the two LED centers is the center of the LED module. If the lower-left corner of the LED frame is the origin of the coordinates, the LEDs are located at $(0, 0, 0)$, $(0, 2, 0)$, $(2, 0, 0)$, $(2, 2, 0)$, and $(1, 1, 0)$. Due to the limitations of the camera's field of view, the ToF camera is placed at a distance of 2.5 m from the wall and 1 m from the ground, which means that ToF is located at $(1, 1, 2.5)$. The FPGA and a power bank which supplies power to the FPGA are also placed in the center of the LED frame. When the experiments are conducted, the five LEDs are ensured to be the only light sources in the room. There are no obstructions in the FOV of ToF camera to affect the experiment, ensuring that the LED and camera are LOS-linked. The entire room was completely in darkness while the experiment carried out.

6.1.2 LED Module

The LED module, as the emitter in the VLP system, plays not only the role of lighting but also positioning reference points (beacons), so the performance of the LED module directly affects the indoor lighting and also to a certain extent determines the accuracy of positioning. Fig. 6.2 illustrates the LED module used in our experiments. It is a dual-LED module composed of two identical LEDs. The LED chip is fixed tightly by screws between the heat sink and LED lens.

LED Lens

The model of the LED lens is CA10953_IRIS-M, which is a 38 mm-diameter round lens. The lens redirects the light from the LED chip to achieve a relatively uniform radiation pattern. The material of the lens is optical-grade Polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) and the lens holder is made of polycarbonate. The Full Width Half Maximum

(a) Demonstration experimental setup.

(b) Top view of the experimental setup.

Figure 6.1: The experimental model for visible light positioning. (a) Five LEDs are mounted on the wall at 2.5 m distance from the camera. (b) FPGA, power bank, and power distributor are placed in the middle of the experimental frame.

Model	Datasheet	Characteristics
LM1086CS-Adj	[110]	1.5 A low dropout positive voltage regulators
EL7156	[111]	Three-state high performance pin driver
IRF8707	[112]	N-Channel So-8 package MOSFET

Table 6.1: LED driver core components.

(FWHM) is used to describe the ability of the lens to diffuse light. The FWHM of the lens we used is $\pm 14.8^\circ$.

LED Driver

The LED driver is also an essential part of the LED module. The performance of the driver directly determines the frequency range in which the LED can be modulated. The assembly diagrams of the drive developed at ZESS within a previous project are shown in Fig. 6.3. The assembled board in Fig. 6.2(b) follows the assembly of Fig. 6.3. This driver is designed to drive up to a maximum of 4 LEDs simultaneously. The core components of the LED driver are shown in Tab. 6.1. From the specifications of the core components, we know that this LED driver has a maximum operating voltage of 12 V, a maximum current of 1 A, and a maximum modulation frequency of 40 MHz.

6.1.3 FPGA

In the experiment we use a model Zybo Z7-20 FPGA from company Xilinx as the generator of the modulation signal, as shown in Fig. 6.4. The board can be powered in many ways: USB, wall wart with barrel jack, and battery pack. We adapt a power bank with USB port to power the board. The Zybo also supports a variety of booting methods, one of which is using a microSB card. We first download the compiled modulation signal generation program to the microSD card, then insert the SD card into the connector J4 of the board, so that the board will run the program on the microSD card when the board is turned on. The board contains two subsystems: Programmable Logic (PL) and

(a) Components of LED modules. (b) The top of the assembled driver board.

(c) The LED chip, whose size exactly matches the size of the lens.

(d) Iris lens for Osram Ostar Lighting LEDs [109].

Figure 6.2: The LED model used in our experiments consists of two identical LED chips with the same lens, which are connected in parallel by a driver.

Figure 6.3: PCB assembly drawing.

Processing System (PS). The board can provide a 50 MHz clock to the PS subsystem, and it can also provide an external 125 MHz clock to the PL. The maximum modulation frequency of the LED driver is 40 MHz, so we have to generate the clock with precise frequency using the Mixed-Mode Clock Manager (MMCM) or Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) provided by the PL. The Zybo contains a number of output ports that can satisfy our experimental purpose of modulating 5 LEDs. On the software front, the Zybo Z7-20 board fully supports Vivado Design Suite by Xilinx. We describe only the parts of the Zybo Z7-20 board that we use to generate signals at different frequencies, the specific description of the Xilinx Zynq-7000 family can be found in [113].

6.1.4 Time-of-Flight Module

As for the choice of ToF camera during the experiment, we selected the “Selene” module with IRS2877C imager from company pmdtechnologies AG, with a resolution of 640×240 . In this experiment the illumination control system of the ToF camera is not used, so the illumination parameters of “Selene” module are not described in detail here. Tab. 6.2 details the specific parameters of the IRS2877C imager for “Selene” module.

Figure 6.4: The ZYBO Zynq-7020 development board.

Figure 6.5: The “Selene” module from Table 6.2: Specific parameters of the IRS2877C imager.

Sensor	Pixel size	5 μm
	Resolution	640 \times 240, VGA
	Sensor size	1/4.5"
	CRA	30°
Lens	F#	1.12
	FOV	D78° H64.3° V50.4°
	EFL	2.49
	RI	50.1%
	CRA	27.1°

6.2 Simulations

In the experiment, we use a FPGA to modulate different LED modules at 3.5 MHz, 7 MHz, 10.5 MHz, 14 MHz, and 17.5 MHz frequencies. The ToF camera needs the same demodulation frequencies to retrieve the raw data without matching errors. The results of the four phase samples acquired by the ToF camera are used to calculate the amplitude and depth image via the “four phases” algorithm. Using the MLE method or EM method to locate the center of the LED on the amplitude image is the key to our algorithm, and subsequent indoor positioning algorithms are based on the known center of the LED. The corresponding depth information of the LED center-point can also be obtained from the depth image. Besides, according to our knowledge about the matrix of lens normals of the camera, the LED center position is determined, which means that the normal of the center point can be obtained. Indoor positioning can be achieved by the AOA algorithm. Indoor localization is also possible using the TDOA algorithm based on the relative distance information obtained from the depth image.

6.2.1 Simulation of Gaussian Mixture Model

Since the LED module is composed of two identical LEDs, we assume that the radiation pattern of the LEDs on the amplitude image obeys a 2D Gaussian distribution. The center coordinates of these two LEDs are $\mu_1 = (1, 1) (m)$ and $\mu_2 = (1, 1.2) (m)$, respectively. X and Y are the random variables associated to the Gaussian distributions. They represent the distribution of the illumination pattern of the LEDs. Consider that they are independent of each other, so the value on the non-diagonal of the covariance is equal to zero. At a distance of 2.5 m, the intensity of received light is quite weak, which leads to a small number of pixels occupied by the illumination patterns of the LEDs on the amplitude image, so we estimate the variance of the system to be $10^{-3} m^2$. The

covariance matrix is expressed as

$$\Sigma_1 = \Sigma_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 10^{-3} & 0 \\ 0 & 10^{-3} \end{bmatrix} (m^2)$$

Meanwhile, Gaussian white noise with 20 dB SNR is added to the Gaussian model of each LED separately. The simulated Gaussian mixture model is shown in Fig. 6.6, where the effect of noise is clearly visible. After receiving the image with Gaussian white noise, We apply bilateral filtering to the image. Bilateral filtering is a nonlinear method that combines spatial proximity and pixel value similarity to achieve edge-preserving for images while filtering. Gaussian filtering only considers the difference in the spatial domain, which will cause blurring at the edges. A weight for the pixel value information is added to the bilateral filtering, i.e., in the neighborhood, points with pixel values closer to the center pixel value have a larger weight, and points with large differences in pixel values have a smaller weight. If the two pixel values are very close (in the flat area), the weight is close to 1, hence it is equivalent to Gaussian filtering. If the pixel values are very different (In the edge area), the weight is close to 0. Therefore the Gaussian filter is not effective and the edges of the image are guaranteed. Intuitively, bilateral filtering will avoid blurring between objects while still removing noise from uniform regions, which fits well with our filtering purpose of both removing noise and preserving the true region of interest. In the current case, we use the standard deviation of the image as the degree of smoothing of the bilateral filter. The spatial extent of the filter (standard deviation of the spatial Gaussian) is set to 7. The filtered image is shown in Fig. 6.7(a).

The filtered image is first normalized, and then the maximum value of the amplitude in the image can be found. Since NLOS links are not considered during the experiment, the maximum value of the amplitude in the image should appear in the area corresponding to the center of the LED (LOS link). We define the region with nor-

malized pixel values greater than 0.1 as the region of interest, which is extracted from the amplitude image, as shown in Fig. 6.7(b). Plugging the observed data into the EM algorithm, convergence is attained after 15 iterations. Fig. 6.8 demonstrate the PDF of the 2D Gaussian mixture model and the corresponding 2D projection based on the system parameters derived by the EM algorithm.

Figure 6.6: A 2-component Gaussian mixture model to simulate the amplitude distribution of LEDs on the amplitude image.

(a) Projection of the filtered GMM.

(b) Extraction of the valid Gaussian distribution area.

Figure 6.7: Simulated amplitude distribution of LEDs on amplitude images

Note that the number of components of the GMM needs to be known in advance. At the initial stage of iteration, the two Gaussian distributions heavily overlap. After 9 iterations, it has been possible to distinguish an independent Gaussian model from the mixture model. After 11 iterations, the two independent Gaussian distributions have been distinguished (no overlap). Starting from the 13th iteration, the two Gaussian

Figure 6.8: The results of 4 key iterations from EM algorithm. From left to right, isolines of the PDF, the PDF of the 2D Gaussian mixture model based on the system parameters and the corresponding 2D projection.

distributions have been completely identified, and the next iterations are only a fine adjustment to achieve the convergence condition.

Fig. 6.9 shows that absolute variation between consecutive iterations of the log-likelihood varies with iterations. It can be observed that the precision of the log-likelihood at the second iteration is already smaller than 0.1, i.e., $|\ell(\theta^2) - \ell(\theta^1)| \leq 0.1$. However, it is clear from Fig. 6.8(b) that the two Gaussian models still overlap.

In other words, a sufficiently small ε is required to guarantee that the correct system parameters are obtained at the end of the iterative process. After several tests, we set the value of ε to 10^{-4} as the iteration stopping condition.

After 15 iterations, the EM process reaches the convergence condition and we obtain the parameters of two independent Gaussian distributions. The obtained mean values are $\hat{\mu}_1 = (1.0006, 1.0008) (m)$ and $\hat{\mu}_2 = (1.0020, 1.2000) (m)$, which are exactly identical to the mean values of the given two Gaussian distributions. The estimated covariance

Figure 6.9: The absolute variation between consecutive iterations of the log-likelihood.

matrices are

$$\hat{\Sigma}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1.1 \times 10^{-3} & -0.6 \times 10^{-5} \\ -0.6 \times 10^{-5} & 0.95 \times 10^{-3} \end{bmatrix} (m^2), \hat{\Sigma}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1.1 \times 10^{-3} & -10^{-9} \\ -10^{-9} & 0.96 \times 10^{-3} \end{bmatrix} (m^2)$$

Two Gaussian models estimated by the EM algorithm have mean values with errors of $\Delta\mu_1 = \hat{\mu}_1 - \mu_1 = (0.6 \times 10^{-3}, 0.8 \times 10^{-3}) (m)$, $\Delta\mu_2 = \hat{\mu}_2 - \mu_2 = (2 \times 10^{-3}, 0) (m)$, respectively. The covariance errors of the Gaussian models are

$$\Delta\Sigma_1 = \hat{\Sigma}_1 - \Sigma_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 10^{-4} & -0.6 \times 10^{-5} \\ -0.6 \times 10^{-5} & -0.5 \times 10^{-4} \end{bmatrix} (m^2),$$

$$\Delta\Sigma_2 = \hat{\Sigma}_2 - \Sigma_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 10^{-4} & -10^{-9} \\ -10^{-9} & -0.4 \times 10^{-4} \end{bmatrix} (m^2)$$

which are approximately equal to the given covariance matrix. By comparing the original and estimated parameters of the two Gaussian models, the error is quite small, which

proves that the EM algorithm can estimate the parameters of the GMM accurately.

In the current test, the two Gaussian models we assume are rotationally-symmetric and unskewed. Once the Gaussian model is skewed, this means that the Gaussian distributed random variables X and Y are no longer independent of each other and their interaction causes the covariance matrix to have non-zero off-diagonal elements, which consequently requires more iterations and a heavy computational burden when using the EM algorithm.

6.2.2 Simulation of Angle of Arrival Algorithm Based on Lens Normal Matrix

By means of the EM algorithm we have found the system parameters in the GMM. We consider the mean value $\mu_i = (x_i, y_i)$ of each Gaussian distribution as the pixel coordinates of the LED center.

As described in Section. 5.3, when we obtain the lens normal matrix and the pixel coordinates of the LED center, we can find the AOA from the corresponding normal vector at the pixel point, and thus use the trigonometric relationship for positioning.

Figure 6.10: The normal on each pixel of the “Selene” module.

In this case, we know the lens normal matrix of a “Selene” module with a resolution of 172×224 . The lens normals are not surface normals of the lens but indicate the

observed direction of the pixels. The red arrow in Fig. 6.10 indicates the normal at each pixel, and the direction of the arrow shows the observed direction at each pixel.

Since the distance between ToF camera and LED frame is kept at 2.5 m, we can consider only the 2D case. The projection of the lens normal in the 2D pixel coordinate system is shown in Fig. 6.11. It can be observed in Fig. 6.11 that all the normal extension lines are not concentrated in pixel (115, 84).

Figure 6.11: The center area of the projection of the normal in the two-dimensional pixel coordinate system. The red lines are the extension lines of the normals of several pixel points.

Using the matrix of lens normals of ToF camera, we calculated that the FOV would be 60.25° horizontally, 46.08° vertically and 70.22° diagonally. Assume that the LEDs are located in the world coordinate system at (0, 0), (0, 2), (2, 0), (2, 2) and (1, 1) respectively. Considering the offset of the camera center, when the camera is located at (1, 1) in the world coordinate system, at a distance of 2.5 m, we can calculate the coordinates of the LEDs in the pixel coordinate system as (37.81, 2.11), (37.81, 164.89),

(192.19, 2.11), (192.19, 164.89) and (115, 84). Since each LED position is a non-integer, the normal vector of the coordinates of each LED can be calculated using interpolation. In combination with Eq. 5.33, Eq. 4.15, and Eq. 4.16, we can estimate the location of the ToF camera, which is (1.0005, 1.0052).

Figure 6.12: AOA algorithm based on lens normal matrix. (a) The pixel coordinates of LED center, and the normal vector at the corresponding pixel point. (b) The world coordinates of LEDs are known and the location of the ToF camera is estimated by the AOA algorithm.

The accuracy of the AOA algorithm depends on the accuracy of the obtained angles. Usually, the AOA is obtained with the help of other sensors, but thanks to the lens normal matrix of the ToF camera, we can find the AOA without other sensors. Once the lens normal matrix of the camera is determined, it is an inherent property of the camera lens, and it does not change with the external experimental scene.

The accuracy of the AOA algorithm based on the lens normal matrix depends on the accuracy of the LED center pixel coordinates. When generating the Ground Truth (GT), we can calculate the LED position in the pixel coordinate system through the geometric relationship between the camera and the LED, so we obtain a very accurate ToF position estimation. However, in practice, the pixel coordinates of the LED center should be given by the system parameters of the GMM calculated from the amplitude image provided by the ToF camera (In the LOS connection system, the coordinates of

the LED center are considered to be the mean values of the Gaussian distributions).

The coordinates of the pixel points are integers, but the parameters of the GMM derived by the EM method are not integers, but decimals. We can approximate the values of the GMM parameters (non-integer points) by interpolating. When we get the coordinates of an LED (37.81, 2.11), because of the non-integer points, it cannot be obtained directly from the matrix of lens normals of the camera. However, we can obtain the coordinates of the four integer points closest to this coordinate, namely, (37, 2), (37, 3), (38, 2) and (38, 3). The non-integer points lie on the plane determined by these four points. The coordinates of the four pixels contain the coordinates of the sample points. By interpolating the normals component on the x-axis and on the y-axis, respectively, we can obtain the normal of the non-integer points.

6.2.3 Simulation of Indoor Localization Based on Time Difference of Arrival Method

With the advantage of not requiring strict clock synchronization between transmitter and receiver, the TDOA algorithm is widely used in positioning systems. The time synchronization between transmitters (LEDs) is easily achieved because they are controlled by the same microcontroller (FPGA). The FPGA generates a set of orthogonal frequency control signals to modulate the LEDs. The ToF camera acquires different images demodulating at the different frequencies. We evaluate the TDOA algorithm using computer simulation.

Simulation of ToF Camera Operation

We perform the simulation according to the experimental setup given in Fig. 6.1. The LEDs are located at (0, 0, 0), (0, 2, 0), (2, 0, 0), (2, 2, 0), and (1, 1, 0). Assume that the modulated sinusoidal signals with frequencies $f_1 = 3.5$ MHz, $f_2 = 7$ MHz,

$f_3 = 10.5$ MHz, $f_4 = 14$ MHz, and $f_5 = 17.5$ MHz are generated by the FPGA and can be expressed as:

$$x_1(t) = \cos(2\pi f_1 t + \phi_0)$$

$$x_2(t) = \cos(2\pi f_2 t + \phi_0)$$

$$x_3(t) = \cos(2\pi f_3 t + \phi_0)$$

$$x_4(t) = \cos(2\pi f_4 t + \phi_0)$$

$$x_5(t) = \cos(2\pi f_5 t + \phi_0)$$

where ϕ_0 denotes the initial phase. Therefore, the mixed signal can be estimated as:

$$x_{\text{mix}}(t) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x_i(t + t_d + \Delta t_i), i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5. \quad (6.1)$$

where a_i denotes the weight of the signal. The larger the a_i , the more weight the signal has in the mixed signal. t_d denotes the time difference between the receiver and transmitter due to non-synchronous time. if $t_d = 0$, it means that the receiver and transmitter are time-synchronous and, thus, TDOA can be considered as TOA. Δt_i is the time difference between the receiver and transmitter due to the absolute distance d_i , with $d_i = c\Delta t_i$. When $\phi_0 = 0$ and the sampling frequency is 840 MHz, the transmitted signals are shown in Fig. 6.13.

We know the coordinates of the LEDs and the coordinates of the ToF camera, so the time difference Δt_i between the transmitted and the received signals can be estimated, with $\Delta t_i = d_i/c$. If we are given t_d and the weights a_i of each signal, we can simulate the mixed signal represented by the Eq. 6.1. x_{mix} denotes the sum of all the modulated light signals in the room before the ToF camera lens. In reality, we cannot get this mixed signal, we can acquire a part of it as the received signal. Fig. 6.14 shows the mixed signal with different t_d . When $t_d = 0$, the received signal and the transmitted signal can be regarded as clock-synchronized, and when $t_d \neq 0$, the mixed signal is

Figure 6.13: When $\phi_0 = 0$, five idealized signals simulated by Matlab.

Figure 6.14: The mixed signal is affected by t_d and Δt_i . When the positions of the LEDs and the ToF camera are fixed, Δt_i does not change, but t_d is uncertain.

Figure 6.15: The mixed signal in the frequency domain.

delayed with t_d . Fig. 6.15 shows the mixed signal in the frequency domain, where we can clearly see the frequency of the signal transmitted from the FPGA. Since the ToF sensor measures the correlation between the transmitted signal and the received signal, we use a cross-correlation function to simulate the computation carried out by each ToF pixel.

$$C_i = (x_i(t) \otimes x_{mix}(t))(\tau)$$

where \otimes denotes cross-correlation. In combination with the “four-phases” algorithm, using Eq. 2.9, the relative distance d'_i of the camera to each LED can be calculated. The relative distance d'_i can also be expressed as: $d'_i = c(t_d + \Delta t_i)$. Although the ToF camera does not measure the real distance between the camera and the LEDs, the distance difference $r_{i,1}$ between the ToF camera to the i -th LED and to the 1-st LED is correct

and given by:

$$\begin{aligned}r_{i,1} &= d'_i - d'_1 \\ &= c(t_d + \Delta t_i) - c(t_d + \Delta t_1) \\ &= c(\Delta t_i - \Delta t_1)\end{aligned}$$

Simulation of TDOA algorithm

Through the abovedescribed simulation of the ToF camera operation, we estimate the distance difference $r_{i,1}$. In the positioning stage, we mainly compared the accuracy of the three TDOA algorithms: Chan's method, Taylor series expansion method, and the hybrid Chan/Taylor method.

According to the experiment model in Fig. 6.1(a), a simulated experimental setup is built for evaluating the accuracy of different methods. In our experiment, 25 test positions (black triangles) for ToF camera are evenly placed in the positioning area with a density of $0.5\text{ m} \times 0.5\text{ m}$. A Gaussian noise with a mean of 0 and a variance of 0.05 m^2 is added to $r_{i,1}$. The results of one of the multiple positioning tests using different methods are shown in Fig. 6.16.

Since the accuracy of the Taylor series expansion method depends on the initial position, if the initial position is particularly outrageously wrong, the final position estimation will also be particularly exhibit a particularly high error. Instead of considering a fixed initial position, we focus on the Taylor series expansion method with the result of the Chan method as the initial position.

In order to perform significance tests, we ran 100 simulations for each test position. If the error of the distance difference is a standard distribution with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 0.05 m^2 , the average results of 100 simulations are shown in Fig. 6.17. It is observed that the results using the hybrid Chan/Taylor method are significantly closer to the test position, i.e., the precision of the results using the hybrid

Figure 6.16: Differences between the ToF test positions and the estimated positions of the three methods (The red “o” is the position of the LEDs, and the black “ Δ ” is the ToF test position. The blue “+” represents the estimated positions obtained by the Chan method. The green “+” is the estimated point obtained by the Taylor series expansion method with the initial position in (0.3, 0.3). The red “+” is the estimated position obtained by the Taylor series expansion method with the result from the Chan method as the initial position.)

Chan/Taylor method is higher than just using the Chan method.

Hypothesis testing is an important element in inferential statistics. It is common to find p-values in hypothesis testing. The P-value is the probability of an observed result assuming the null hypothesis is true. The smaller the p-value, the less probability there is that the null hypothesis is correct. Therefore, the stronger the evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The significance level(α) is the threshold of the P-value for rejecting the null hypothesis and is generally taken as 5%. For our experiments, we propose a null hypothesis (\mathbf{H}_0) and an alternative hypothesis (\mathbf{H}_a), which are expressed as:

$$\mathbf{H}_0 : P_{est} - P_{test} = 0 \text{ or } P_{est} = P_{test}$$

$$\mathbf{H}_a : P_{est} - P_{test} \neq 0 \text{ or } P_{est} \neq P_{test}$$

where P_{est} contains the 100 estimated positions and P_{test} is the position of the test position. The null hypothesis can also be interpreted as the error values of the estimated and test positions are from a normal distribution with the mean equal to zero. Tab. 6.3 and Tab. 6.4 show the p-values of the errors at each test position using Chan's method and the hybrid Chan/Taylor method, respectively. At most test positions, P-values are greater than 0.05 which indicate that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected at the default 5% significance level. When the p-value using the Chan method is less than 0.05, the p-value of the hybrid Chan/Taylor method based on the Chan method will also be less than 0.05.

P-Value (P_x, P_y) \ X (m) Y (m)	0	0.5	1	1.5	2
0	(0.073, 0.090)	(0.547, 10^{-10})	(0.460, 0.589)	(0.774, 10^{-5})	(0.670, 10^{-25})
0.5	(10^{-5} , 0.632)	(0.871, 0.851)	(0.256, 0.145)	(0.109, 0.912)	(0.793, 0.633)
1	(0.575, 0.457)	(0.814, 0.620)	(0.862, 0.825)	(0.891, 0.895)	(0.646, 0.160)
1.5	(10^{-5} , 0.776)	(0.519, 0.470)	(0.865, 0.227)	(0.510, 0.166)	(0.108, 0.837)
2	(10^{-20} , 0.026)	(0.339, 0.499)	(0.813, 0.400)	(0.826, 0.030)	(0.938, 0.748)

Table 6.3: P-value of the error value using the Chan method.

Figure 6.17: Results of 100 simulations for each test position.

P-Value (P_x, P_y)	X (m)				
	0	0.5	1	1.5	2
Y (m)					
0	(0.073, 0.090)	(0.307, 10^{-8})	(0.168, 0.060)	(0.351, 0.991)	(10^{-5} , 0.005)
0.5	(10^{-4} , 0.625)	(0.781, 0.780)	(0.411, 0.073)	(0.133, 0.315)	(0.744, 0.541)
1	(0.455, 0.575)	(0.950, 0.676)	(0.247, 0.125)	(0.821, 0.722)	(0.895, 0.747)
1.5	(0.950, 0.007)	(0.535, 0.166)	(0.747, 0.183)	(0.461, 0.073)	(0.287, 0.380)
2	(0.035, 0.005)	(0.076, 0.425)	(0.795, 0.500)	(0.720, 0.023)	(10^{-9} , 10^{-11})

Table 6.4: P-value of the error value using the hybrid Chan/Taylor method.

Fig. 6.18 depicts the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of the estimated position with different methods versus SNR of the distance between the LED and The ToF camera r_i when the ToF camera is at (0.5, 0.5). The RMSE is often used to measure the deviation between the observed and true values and is expressed as:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (P_{\text{est}} - P_{\text{test}})^2} \quad (6.2)$$

where P_{est} are the estimated positions, P_{test} are the test positions, and n the number of

simulations. In our experiments, $n = 10000$.

Figure 6.18: The RMSE of TDOA algorithm with the Chan method and the hybrid Chan/Taylor method.

In parameter estimation and statistics, the Cramér-Rao Bound (CRB) [114] determines a lower bound for the variance of any unbiased estimator. Commonly, CRB can be used to calculate the best estimation accuracy that can be obtained in unbiased estimation. Therefore, it is possible to evaluate the performance of parameter estimation methods by comparing the closeness to the CRB.

By observing Fig. 6.18, all three methods have good performance in position estimation. When the initial position is $(0.3, 0.3)$, the RMSE obtained by the Taylor series expansion method are closest to the CRB for low SNR. When the SNR is greater than 100 dB, the RMSE does not change as the SNR becomes greater because the error starts to be smaller than the convergence condition ε . The Chan method and the hybrid Chan/Taylor method are closely follow the CRB. Moreover, the hybrid Chan/Taylor method is closer than the Chan method, which means that the hybrid Chan/Taylor method has better performance for estimating the position. Taking into account both

the p-value and the RMSE, it becomes apparent that the estimated position by the Chan method has high precision, but the hybrid Chan/Taylor can further improve the precision of positioning.

6.3 Experimental Validations

In Sec. 6.2, we have verified the GMM based on the EM algorithm and the TDOA algorithm based on the hybrid Chan/Taylor method via computer simulations. In this section, we will experimentally demonstrate our proposed algorithms.

6.3.1 Signal Generation by FPGA

The Zynq-Z7020 is the chosen FPGA model, which provides a PL with 125 MHz clock frequency, and it includes a MMCM and a PLL that can be used directly. We control the FPGA by using Vivado Design Suite (2020.2). The frequencies we used in the simulation are $f_1 = 3.5$ MHz, $f_2 = 2 \times 3.5$ MHz, $f_3 = 3 \times 3.5$ MHz, $f_4 = 4 \times 3.5$ MHz, and $f_5 = 5 \times 3.5$ MHz. We can select PLL or MMCM in the clocking wizard configuration interface to generate these five different clock frequencies. Due to the limitations of the chip, the required frequencies are not always available. Comparing the 50 MHz clock frequency of PS and the 125 MHz clock frequency of PL, the 125 MHz of PL can be used to generate more precise frequencies.

Since the 3.5 MHz clock frequency is lower than the minimum frequency generated by the clocking wizard, we use the strategy of frequency multiplication followed by frequency division. Due to hardware circuit limitations, integers are typically used for exact frequency multiplication and division. The least common multiple of the set of required frequencies is 60×3.5 MHz = 210 MHz, which can be perfectly output by the clocking wizard when the input is the PL reference clock at 125 MHz. Meanwhile, the 210 MHz clock frequency can be used to obtain the desired five frequencies by dividing

60, 30, 20, 15, and 12, respectively. Fig. 6.19 illustrates the block diagram of clocking wizard, where `clk_in1` is the reference clock frequency of PL (125 MHz), `clk_out1` is the output clock frequency (210 MHz), and `locked` indicates the stability of the output clocks.

Figure 6.19: Block diagram of clocking wizard.

After the frequency multiplication is completed, it is necessary to perform four even divisions and one odd division of the obtained frequency. The even divider is easy to achieve and can be fully implemented by counting. If an N -times even frequency division is carried out, the counter can be triggered by the clock, and when the counter counts from 0 to $N/2 - 1$, the output clock is flipped, and a reset signal is given to the counter so that the next clock starts counting from zero. In this cycle, it is possible to achieve any even frequency division. If the odd frequency division is followed by the even frequency division method, the clock frequency of the odd frequency division can also be obtained, but the duty cycle is not 50%, which can not satisfy our requirements. However, combining the intermediate clock block and doing some logical “AND” and “OR” operations odd frequency division with 50% duty cycle can be achieved.

The odd frequency division method we used is as follows: a counter with an initial value of 0 counts on the rising edge, and when the count value is 1, the output clock is flipped once, then the count continues, and when the count reaches $(15 - 1)/2 + 2 = 9$, the clock is flipped again, and when the count reaches $15 - 1 = 14$, the counter is reset to zero and repeat the above process. The other counter with an initial value of 0 counts

on the falling edge and performs the same operation as the one operating on rising edge. By the “AND” operation of the two obtained divider clocks, the final 50% duty cycle of a 15 division is obtained. Fig. 6.20 shows the simulation diagram of frequency division by 15, where clk_1_3 is the divided clock obtained by counting on the rising edge, clk_2_3 is the divided clock obtained by counting on the falling edge, and out_1_3 is the frequency divided by 15 with 50% duty cycle after the “AND” operation.

Figure 6.20: Simulation diagram of frequency division by 15, $f = \frac{1}{71.429 \text{ ns}} = 14 \text{ MHz}$.

According to the above method, we generated five requested clock frequencies with a duty cycle of 50%. Nevertheless, a new problem arises: the odd division’s clock is one clock cycle behind the even division, which leads to no simultaneous triggering of the five signals. In order to solve this problem, we add a D flip-flop after the output of the even frequency division, which can achieve a delay of one clock cycle, so that the five signals are triggered simultaneously.

The schematic for generating the desired clock frequencies is shown in Fig. B.2. The results of the simulation are depicted in Fig. 6.21. The five clock frequencies are triggered simultaneously and each clock frequency is ensured to have a 50% duty cycle. The multiplicative relationship between the five frequencies is also well maintained, with $f_1 = \frac{1}{285.715 \text{ ns}} = 3.5 \text{ MHz}$.

Figure 6.21: Simulation results for the five requested clock frequencies.

6.3.2 Expectation-Maximization Algorithm in Gaussian Mixture Model

In Sec. 6.2.1, we discussed the GMM obtained by computer simulation and demonstrate that the EM algorithm can be used for parameter estimation of the GMM with good results. In this section, we control the “Selene” module with IRS2877C imager via python to capture the LED signals modulated by the FPGA.

Since the ToF camera is only used as a passive module in our experiments, we modified the startup program to disable the illumination module before the experiment in order to avoid interference from the illumination source that comes with the ToF module.

Recall that the ToF sensor utilizes four samples of the correlation between the transmitted and received signals to calculate the phase difference through the “four-phase” algorithm and thereby calculate the distance. Therefore, the frequency matching of the transmit and receive signals becomes critical. In the active ToF camera, the modulated and demodulated signals can be generated by the same controller, and the frequency matching is simple to achieve. In the passive ToF camera, the modulated signal is generated by the FPGA and the demodulated signal is produced by the ToF camera, which makes frequency matching difficult to achieve. The maximum modulation frequency that the driver of the LED module can carry is 40 MHz, but through testing we found that when the modulation frequency is greater than 19 MHz, the modulation signal from the LED module can no longer be detected by an PD. Because the amplitude of the modulated signal is so low, only small fluctuations can be seen from the oscilloscope, but the frequency cannot be obtained. Therefore, the maximum modulation frequency of our experiment cannot exceed 19 MHz.

	f_1 (MHz)	f_2 (MHz)	f_3 (MHz)	f_4 (MHz)	f_5 (MHz)
FPGA	3.51383	7.02765	10.54125	14.05521	17.56913
ToF module	3.51400	7.02800	10.54200	14.05600	17.57000

Table 6.5: Comparison between the frequencies provided by FPGA and the frequencies of ToF module.

Due to hardware limitations, the frequency available from the FPGA does not perfectly match the frequency of the ToF module. The frequencies of the ToF module and the frequency that the FPGA can provide to best match the ToF module are listed in Tab. 6.5. Most of the mismatches between them are less than 1 KHz, and considering

the effects of other factors in the experimental system, we regard the mismatch of 1 KHz to be acceptable.

Figure 6.22: Results obtained by the “Selene” module in four phases when the LED module is in the middle and modulated at 3.5 MHz.

We first tested the case when only the center LED was modulated at 3.5 MHz by the FPGA and the ToF module was placed 2.5 m away from the center LED. Fig. 6.22 shows the results of four-phase samples obtained by the “Selene” module. It is observed that the LED module can be clearly distinguished in each of the four phases.

With the help of the “four-phases” algorithm, the amplitude image and the depth image can be calculated and are shown in Fig. 6.23. By comparing Fig. 6.23(a) and Fig. 6.7(a), it becomes apparent that the real amplitude image is very similar to the amplitude image estimated by our simulation. Therefore, we can follow the process exactly as in Sec. 6.2.1. The valid observations in the amplitude image are extracted after filtering and normalizing, as shown in Fig. 6.24(a). The system parameters of the GMM are estimated after 11 iterations of the EM algorithm. From the 8th iteration, the change of iterations is no longer perceptible, but it can be seen in Fig. 6.26 that the absolute variation between consecutive iterations of log-likelihood does not reach the

convergence condition $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$.

Figure 6.23: The amplitude image and depth image are obtained by the “Selene” module using the “four phases” algorithm, when the LED module is in the middle and modulated at 3.5 MHz.

The system parameters (red “+”) of the GMM after 11 iterations of the EM algorithm are plotted in Fig. 6.24(b). As a comparison, the center of gravity point (green “.”) is also plotted. The center of the line connecting the mean values of the two independent Gaussian distributions (i.e., the center point of the LED module) is denoted by red “*”. In the current case, the center point of the LED module and the center of gravity point almost coincide.

For comparison, we also investigate the performance of the EM algorithm for GMM parameter estimation with the ZESS MultiCam [115] [116] as the receiver at the same position. The MultiCam, together with selected lens, which can cover the scene at 2.5 m

(a) The extracted valid observation area (b) The extracted original amplitude image and the results of the GMM

Figure 6.24: Amplitude image and valid observation area obtained by the “Selene” module, when the LED module is in the middle. (a) Extracted, after filtering and normalization, the extracted valid observation area in the amplitude image. (b) The original amplitude image corresponding to the valid observation area and the results of the GMM.

Figure 6.25: The results of 4 out of 11 iterations of the EM algorithm, when the “Selene” module is used and the LED module is in the middle.

Figure 6.26: The absolute variation between consecutive iterations of the log-likelihood, when the “Selene” module is used and the LED module is in the middle.

distance, are shown in Fig. 6.27. Similarly, the illumination control system is not used.

The parameters of the MultiCam are shown in Tab. 6.6.

MultiCam	Resolution	2D: 2048(H) \times 1536(V) 3D: 160(H) \times 120(V)
	Frame rate	12fps (80fps with reduced 2D resolution)
	Camera Body size	80 \times 85 \times 120 mm ³
Lens	Model	LM6NC3
	Focal length	6 mm
	F#	1.8 - 16
	FOV (1/1.8”)	D78.8° H65.3° V50.1°

Table 6.6: The parameters of the MultiCam.

The amplitude image obtained by the MultiCam, the extracted image after filtering and normalization are shown in Fig. 6.28. The results of the system parameters after 21 iterations are plotted in Fig. 6.28(b). Comparing Fig. 6.28(b) and Fig. 6.24(b), we can observe that the “Selene” module can acquire more valid observations than the ZESS MultiCam at a distance of 2.5 m due to its higher resolution. The Multicam has a significant overlap between the two independent Gaussian distributions due to the

(a) Multicam is surrounded by illumination system consisting of 13 dual LED modules.

(b) Model LM6NC3.

Figure 6.27: The ZESS MultiCam and the selected lens.

low resolution. When the LED is in the middle and the camera is directly in front of the LED, the “Selene” module and the MultiCam can recognize the two Gaussian distributions and both system parameters can be estimated by using the EM algorithm.

When an LED located in the corner is modulated and the ToF camera is still in the center, the results of the four phases obtained by the “Selene” module are shown in Fig. 6.29.

Because the LED is located in the corner, it results that the ToF sensor collect fewer photons. Comparing Fig. 6.22 and Fig. 6.29, when the LED is in the center, it is easy to identify the LED in all four phases. However, when the LED is in the corner, it is difficult to recognize the LED in all four phases, especially in phase 0° (Fig. 6.29(a)) and phase 90° (Fig. 6.29(b)).

(a) The extracted valid observation area in the amplitude image. (b) The extracted original amplitude image and the results of the GMM.

Figure 6.28: Amplitude image and valid observation obtained by the Zess MultiCam, when the LED module is in the middle. (a) Extracted, after filtering and normalization, the extracted valid observation area in the amplitude image. (b) The original amplitude image corresponding to the valid observation area and the results of the GMM.

Figure 6.29: Results obtained by the “Selene” module in four phases when the LED module is in the bottom-left and modulated at 3.5 MHz.

Figure 6.30: The amplitude image and depth image are obtained by the “Selene” module using the “four phases” algorithm, when the LED module is in the bottom-left.

As shown in Fig. 6.30(a), the amplitude of the LED (around 20) is not much higher than the amplitude of the surrounding pixels (close to 0). LED occupies very few pixels on the amplitude image and is very difficult to observe. The few occupied pixels translates into few valid observations for the EM algorithm, which can lead to inaccuracies in the estimated parameters. As observed by Fig. 6.31(a), only a small amount of data can be used as observations for the EM algorithm. Despite the small amount of observed data, the system parameters of the GMM were obtained after 19 iterations using the EM algorithm. From the 6th iteration shown in Fig. 6.32(a), two independent Gaussian distributions can be distinguished, but the distortion is strong due to the inaccuracy of the system parameters. In the 8th iteration shown in Fig. 6.32(b), one of the Gaussian

distributions has been determined. In the 16th iteration shown in Fig. 6.32(d), the two Gaussian distributions have been separated. By comparing the 18th iteration with the 19th iteration, only a small differences can be observed in the PDF images of the Gaussian distribution. Fig. 6.33 shows the absolute variation between consecutive iterations of the log-likelihood, when the LED module is in the corner.

Figure 6.31: Amplitude image and valid observation area obtained by the “Selene” module, when LED module is in the bottom-left. (a) Extracted, after filtering and normalization, the extracted valid observation area in the amplitude image. (b) The original amplitude image corresponding to the valid observation area and the results of the GMM.

For comparison, the extracted image of the amplitude image acquired by the Multi-Cam is shown in Fig. 6.34, when the LED is in the corner. After 24 iterations, the mean values of the two Gaussian distributions are plotted in Fig. 6.34(b).

Comparing Fig. 6.34(a) and Fig. 6.31(a), the number of valid data is approximately the same, but due to the low resolution of the MultiCam, the two Gaussian distributions are mixed together. When the LED is in the corner, there is a large difference between the center point of the LED module and the center of gravity point.

With too few valid observations, the EM algorithm will most likely not work properly when the LED is in the corner. The difference between the amplitude of the LED and

Figure 6.32: The results of 6 out of 19 iterations of the EM algorithm, when the “Selene” module is used and the LED is in the bottom-left.

Figure 6.33: The absolute variation between consecutive iterations of the log-likelihood, when the “Selene” module is used and LED is in the the bottom-left.

(a) The extracted valid observation area in the amplitude image. (b) The extracted original amplitude image and the results of the GMM.

Figure 6.34: Amplitude image and valid observation area obtained by the MultiCam, when LED module is in the bottom-left. (a) Extracted, after filtering and normalization, the extracted valid observation area in the amplitude image. (b) The original amplitude image corresponding to the valid observation area and the results of the GMM.

the amplitude of the surrounding pixels is so small that the distribution of the LED cannot be stably observed in the amplitude image in most attempts of the experiment, because a tiny error may exceed the amplitude of the LED.

When five LEDs are modulated simultaneously, the ToF sensors collect many photons from the center LED because the camera has to be placed directly in front of the center LED in order to cover the entire LED frame. Only a few photons from the LEDs at the corners are received. The intensity of the light from the center modulated LED is much greater than the light from the LEDs at the corners, making the LEDs at the corners indistinguishable in the amplitude image.

7 Discussion

We propose a novel indoor localization method exploiting ToF imaging for OWP. Through computer simulations and physical tests of the core technologies, we demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed localization method. However, there are still considerable gaps between theoretical simulations and practical experiments in implementing the algorithm, and many critical points need to be taken into account.

In wireless communication, matching the modulated signal and demodulated signal frequency is the key to distortion-free demodulation. The frequency matching problem becomes a thorny issue due to the absence of synchronism between transmitter and receiver. As shown in Tab. 6.5, in our experiments, the clock frequency generated by the FPGA and the frequency of the ToF module are not exactly matched. However, given the influence of various factors during the experiment and the fact that the mismatch (< 1 KHz) is too small relative to the chosen frequency (over 3.5 MHz), the error caused by the mismatch was still acceptable. Nevertheless, the phase difference error due to frequency mismatch is unpredictable in practice. Hence, the guarantee of matching the clock frequency provided by the FPGA and the frequency of the ToF module is a necessary condition for accurate positioning. Since the available operating frequencies for consumer-grade ToF modules are determined at the design stage, an economical solution is to select an FPGA that can match the frequency of the selected ToF module. A general solution is to adopt a high-performance FPGA that can provide arbitrary clock frequencies, but the high-performance FPGA may increase the overall cost of the positioning solution.

When modulating LEDs, the choice of modulation frequency is bounded by the bandwidth of the LED and its driver. In our experiment, the theoretical modulation

frequency can reach 40 MHz. However, in the test, when the frequency is over 19 MHz, it is already difficult to resolve the LED frequency on the PD, so the theoretical modulation frequency range can only provide an upper bound for the maximum modulation frequency, but the actual performance of the LED module needs to be obtained through preliminary. Despite limited modulation frequency range, the driver of the LED module suffered from overheating. Therefore, it is necessary to consider not only the performance of the components, but also the heat dissipation when designing the driver.

The maximum modulation frequency we use is about 17.5 MHz, which is within the empirical range of modulation frequency of the LED module. However, during the experiment, the FPGA provided five different clock frequencies properly, but one of the modulation signals (note as f_x) could not be detected on the PD. After extensive experiments, we found out that the LED module was not modulated at the frequency 17.57 MHz. Thereby, the PD did not receive the modulated signal from the LED. By analyzing each step of the experiment, the cause of this issue was identified. As shown in the Fig. 6.4, the Zynq-7020 board contains multiple I/O modules. In order to clearly distinguish the different modulation frequencies, we used different I/O modules. Due to the internal circuit of FPGA, the output voltage of each I/O module is not identical. Owing to the resistance of the connecting wires and connectors, the voltage of the modulated signal is so low that it cannot trigger the driver element (EL7156). After changing the output port, this problem was solved. This problem enlightened us that in subsequent experiments, the output port voltage of the modulated signal needs to be noticed, the same I/O module should be chosen for different modulated signals, and the resistance of the wires and connectors should be taken into account. Eventually, additional level-adaptation circuitry may be required.

Because of the FOV limitation of the ToF module, the distance between the ToF module and the LED frame had to be increased to 2.5 m in order to cover the size of the

LED frame ($2\text{ m} \times 2\text{ m}$). According to Eq. 4.6, the increase in the distance leads to a decrease in the intensity of the received light, which may be one of the reasons for the failure to recognize the LEDs at the corners of the amplitude image. A simple solution is to reduce the size of the LED frames. An alternative solution could be to increase the number of LEDs within the LED frame. If the geometry of the emitter system is given, the FOV of the ToF camera will have to be adjusted accordingly by choosing an appropriate lens.

According to the current experimental model, using Eq. 4.6, the intensity of received light when the LED is in the center is 60 times greater than when the LED is in the corner. The mixed signal is an idealized signal where the mixed signals appear in free space propagation, before the camera lens. When the signals are received by the camera, they are focused on different regions of the array of ToF pixels. In practice, interference can exist due to MPI between the signal and the ToF pixels and NLOS effects. Therefore the spectrum diagram of the received mixed signal is likely to be as depicted in Fig. 7.1. The frequency with the highest amplitude depends on the LED, which is closest to the ToF module. In comparison, the amplitude of the other frequencies is so small that they have a negligible contribution to the resulting mixed signal. Since increasing the driving voltage increases the amplitude, we studied the effect of the driving voltage from 8.5 V to 11.5 V (maximum LED driver voltage up to 12 V) on the amplitude, as shown in Tab. 7.1. When the voltage is below 10.050 V, the single LED in the corner is unobserved on the amplitude image. When the voltage is between 10.050 V and 10.555 V, the LED located in the corner can be roughly recognized on the four phase images. Still, the LED cannot be recognized on the amplitude image calculated via the “four phases” algorithm. In the voltage range of 10.555 V to 10.652 V, a single LED in the center or in the corner can be observed. However, when two LEDs are modulated at the same time, only the LED in the center can be observed, and the LED in the corner

is difficult to distinguish from the surrounding pixels because there is no significant difference between the amplitude of the LED and that of the surrounding pixels. When the voltage is greater than 10.652 V, and overexposure occurs in the central area of the amplitude image.

Changing the exposure time is also an option to increase the amplitude. In practice, one could use different exposure times at different frequencies by modifying the firmware, but since it is uncertain which LED modules appear in which areas of the amplitude image, it is not practical to artificially modify the exposure frequency frequently. A better alternative is to use dynamically adjusted exposure times. AHDR overcomes accidental saturation by dynamically adjusting the exposure time. HDR algorithms take different acquisitions at different exposure times, in order to capture both intensely-illuminated areas in low-exposed acquisitions without saturation, but also darker areas in high-exposed acquisitions [117].

LED voltage (V)	LED position		
	Center	Corner	Center + Corner
8.505	Observable	Unobservable	Only Center LED observable
10.050	Observable	LED can be observed in four phase diagrams, but is unobservable after calculation	Only Center LED observable
10.555	Observable	Observable	Only Center LED observable
10.652	Overexposure	Observable	NA

Table 7.1: Effect of LED driving voltage on the observability of the LED modules in the amplitude images when the exposure time is 2.2 ms.

Figure 7.1: The spectrum diagram of the received mixed signal. Suppose that the center LED module modulated by 3.5 MHz is the main contributor and the PD is located near the center LED module.

Figure 7.2: The improved system model with nine VCSELs and a receiver.

The LED module used in this work is composed of dual LEDs, as shown in Fig. 6.2(a). We use the EM algorithm on the amplitude images to find the centers of the LED modules, shown as “red *” in Fig. 6.24(b) and Fig. 6.31(b). Suppose that the coordinates of the center point of the LED module are used to obtain the corresponding distance on the depth image. This would actually bring an unknown error and thus lead to a failure of localization. The amplitude corresponding to the center point of the LED module is too low, resulting in an unreliable estimated distance, since the amplitude relates to the accuracy of the depth information. We can see that the amplitude of the center point of each LED is high, but the amplitude of the center point of the LED module is particularly low, which indicates that the distance estimation of the center point of the LED module is inaccurate. Observe, for instance, Fig. 6.31(b), where we

see that there is no difference between the amplitude of the center of the LED module and the amplitude of the surrounding pixels. If five uncertain distance values are used in the TDOA algorithm to estimate the position of the ToF module, the accuracy of the positioning cannot be guaranteed. A simple solution would be to use a single LED instead of an LED module. Furthermore, LEDs are now gradually being replaced by VCSELs due to their high power consumption and low modulation frequency of the former, so using VCSELs would be a better choice. Alternatively, increasing the number of LEDs in the LED module allows the LED module to be approximated to a single LED, as shown in Fig. 5.6(b). Although the distance of the center of the LED module is inaccurate and an accurate position estimation cannot be obtained by the TDOA algorithm, the AOA algorithm(Fig. 7.3(c)) is accurate because the normal vector of the center of the LED module can be accurately determined.

Figure 7.3: The error distribution of the estimated positions when adding Gaussian noise with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 0.05 m^2 .

In the localization phase, we used the TDOA algorithm based on Chan's method, but Chan's method also has limitations. As shown in Fig. 7.3, the positioning error obtained when the ToF camera is located at the boundary of the LED frame is larger than when the ToF camera is located within the LED frame. Comparing Chan's method in Fig. 7.3(a) with the hybrid Chan/Taylor method in Fig. 7.3(b), it is obvious that using the hybrid Chan/Taylor method can improve the accuracy near the borders. It also explains why the p-value is less than 0.05 at the boundaries of the LED frame, especially at the four corners. A good verification of this is also found in Fig. 6.17, where the estimated positions in the four corners are far from the test point compared to the other estimated positions.

The performance of the ToF camera is also a major factor affecting the localization accuracy. A high-performance ToF camera with high resolution can acquire more valid data points at the same distance. For example, comparing Fig. 6.24(b) and Fig. 6.28(b), it can be observed that the "Selene" module collects more valid observations than the MultiCam. In addition, because the calculated system parameters are not integers, the depth estimation of the corresponding points cannot be obtained directly from the depth image. We have to use interpolation to estimate the distances of non-integer points. Interpolation results are more accurate when the density of sampling points is high, as when using high-resolution cameras. Combining more accurate system parameter estimation and more accurate interpolation results in higher localization accuracy for high-performance cameras. The principle of the ToF camera uses sinusoidal signals, but, in practice, both the modulation signals from the FPGA and the pixel control signals from the ToF camera are close to (smoothed) square waves, which results in a (smoothed) triangular wave with odd amplitudes of $\frac{1}{n^2}$ instead of a sinusoid in the cross-correlation. Regarding the rise time and the time period (frequency), an increase of the modulation frequency yields a close-sinusoidal signal. Apart from that, a LUT [23] [24]

can also be used to compensate the effect of harmonic distortion on the measurements and obtain an accurate distance measurement.

Considering the above discussion, we propose an improved experimental model with nine VCSELs instead of the original five LEDs in a $2\text{ m} \times 2\text{ m}$ LED frame, as shown in Fig. 7.2. VCSEL diodes have the advantages of small size, long lifetime, and high modulation frequency. A high-performance FPGA can provide above 1 GHz modulation frequency signals for controlling the VCSELs. High-performance ToF cameras could acquire the raw images corresponding to the nine modulated signals simultaneously in real time. The higher modulation frequency and higher density of emitters of the suggested layout theoretically allow for higher positioning accuracy.

8 Conclusions

In this paper, we propose an indoor positioning system based on OWP using arrays of ToF pixels. One contribution of our proposed system is the successful combination of a visible light indoor localization algorithm and a passive ToF camera. The amplitude image and depth image of the ToF camera are used to obtain the position of the indoor LED modules and the relative distances between the LED modules and the camera. Then, the localization is achieved using both the AOA and TDOA techniques.

We demonstrate that the Gaussian model can approximate the illumination distribution based on the Lambertian radiation model, thus providing a mathematical basis for estimating the distribution of LEDs on the amplitude image with a Gaussian mixture model.

We simulate the performance of the system at a range of 2.5 m using a size of LED frame $2\text{ m} \times 2\text{ m}$. The EM algorithm can estimate the system parameters of the GMM model accurately with the acquisition of sufficient valid observation data. The AOA algorithm based on the matrix of lens normals of the “Selene” ToF camera (resolution: 172x224) exhibits the best localization performance using the least squares method. By means of computer simulations, it is proved that the use of the hybrid Chan/Taylor method can compensate for the errors due to the limitations of the Chan method to a certain extent for estimating the position via TDOA. We have carried out a hypothesis test on the errors of the position estimation through extensive simulations, and the results show that the p-values are greater than 5% at all points except at the limit points of the Chan method, which indicates that the null hypothesis (the errors come from a normal distribution with mean value 0) cannot be rejected at the default significant level of 5%.

Our experiments demonstrate the feasibility of the algorithms applied to real data acquired with the proposed system. Five LEDs are successfully modulated simultaneously by the FPGA. The system parameters of the Gaussian model are accurately estimated using the EM algorithm with observed data consisting of filtered and normalized points extracted from the amplitude image. In addition, we compare the effect of the performance two ToF cameras, namely, the “Selene” module and the MultiCam, on the estimation of LED center points using the EM algorithm and find that the use of a high-performance ToF camera significantly increases the number of valid data points, leading to improved accuracy. However, when the LED appears close to a corner of the ToF image plane, the intensity of the light received by the ToF camera is so weak that it is difficult to distinguish the LED on the amplitude image, so we propose an improved experimental model with nine VCSELs.

In this paper, we have verified that it is feasible to attain light-based positioning using the proposed system, exploiting known AOA and TDOA techniques through both computer simulations and experiments. However, the final localization results were not obtained in the experiments due to limitations of the current experimental equipment. In light of the current experimental results, success with the new experimental setup is to be expected. As future work, we can conduct experiments based on the proposed improved experimental setup, where nine VCSELs and a high-performance FPGA will be employed. The advantageous effect of high-frequency modulation beyond 100 MHz or even up to 1 GHz on the accuracy of our proposed positioning system will also be investigated in the future. Enhancement of the accuracy of the positioning estimate will be also pursued in the future by means of probabilistic filtering approaches, such as Kalman filters or particle filters.

Appendices

A Gaussian Distribution Function

A.1 Univariate Gaussian Distribution function

Univariate Gaussian function is given as:

$$P(x | \mu, \sigma^2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where μ is the mean value, which indicates the center of the Gaussian distribution. σ is standard deviation, which indicates the shape of the Gaussian distribution. σ^2 is often known as the variance.

A.2 Multivariate Gaussian Distribution function

The n-dimensional gaussian distribution function is given by:

$$P(\mathbf{x} | \mu, \Sigma) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^d |\Sigma|}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x} - \mu)^T \Sigma^{-1} (\mathbf{x} - \mu)\right) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where \mathbf{x} is a n-dimensional vector of random variables, μ is the vector of means and $|\Sigma|$ is the variance-covariance matrix.

When $n = 2$, two-dimensional vector of variables $\mathbf{x} = [X, Y]^T$ has the bivariate normal distribution with a corresponding vector of means $\mu = [\mu_X, \mu_Y]$ and covariance matrix

$$\Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_X^2 & \rho\sigma_X\sigma_Y \\ \rho\sigma_X\sigma_Y & \sigma_Y^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

where ρ is the correlation between X and Y . Hence, the 2-dimensional Gaussian distribution function is given by:

$$f(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_X\sigma_Y\sqrt{1-\rho^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2(1-\rho^2)} \left[\left(\frac{x-\mu_X}{\sigma_X}\right)^2 - 2\rho \left(\frac{x-\mu_X}{\sigma_X}\right) \left(\frac{y-\mu_Y}{\sigma_Y}\right) + \left(\frac{y-\mu_Y}{\sigma_Y}\right)^2 \right]\right) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

When X and Y are independent of each other, i.e. $\rho = 0$, the Eq. A.3 can be simplified as:

$$f(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_X\sigma_Y} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-\mu_X}{\sigma_X}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y-\mu_Y}{\sigma_Y}\right)^2 \right]\right) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

A.3 The 2D Fourier Transform

When $\mu = [0, 0]$, $\sigma_X = \sigma_Y$, according to the separability we can get:

$$f(x, y) = f(x)f(y)$$

,

$$f(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{x^2 + y^2}{\sigma^2}\right)$$

The two-dimensional Fourier transform $F(u, v)$ can be expanded as:

$$\begin{aligned} F(u, v) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma)^2} \exp\left(-\frac{(x^2 + y^2)}{2\sigma^2}\right) \exp(-j2\pi(ux + vy)) dx dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \exp(-j2\pi ux) dx \\ &\quad \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \exp(-j2\pi vy) dy \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Due to $F(u, v) = F(u)F(v)$, the Fourier transform $F(u)$ is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(u) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} e^{-2\pi i u x} dx \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} [\cos(2\pi u x) - i \sin(2\pi u x)] dx \\
 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} \cos(2\pi u x) dx - i \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} \sin(2\pi u x) dx \quad (\text{A.6}) \\
 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-2\pi^2 u^2 \sigma^2} \\
 &= e^{-2\pi^2 u^2 \sigma^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$F(u, v) = \exp(-2\pi^2 \sigma^2 (u^2 + v^2)) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

B Schematic Diagrams

The hardware schematic of the LED driver we use is shown in Fig. B.1.

Figure B.1: Hardware schematic of LED driver.

The modulation signal “Mod-in” enters the driver from port ST8. Because pin OE in the EL7156 is continuously high, the EL7156 is always on, output voltage “Trig1” alternately outputs VH and VL as the frequency of the modulation signal changes, and the output voltage supplies the LED through IRF8707.

Five different frequencies are generated using the FPGA, where four even frequency

divisions and one odd frequency division are performed. The hardware circuit diagram for generating the five frequencies is shown in Fig. B.2. The blue block is the called clocking wizard, and the red block is the D-trigger to ensure synchronization.

Figure B.2: Schematic diagram of the five desired clock frequency generation. The blue block shows the clocking wizard, and the red block contains four D-triggers added for synchronization.

C Experimental Results of The MultiCam

The parameters of the two Gaussian distributions are finally determined after 21 iterations using the MultiCam when the LED is located at the center. In the 7th iteration shown in Fig. C.1(a), the two Gaussians are still overlapped. Starting from the 8th iteration, the two Gaussians are separated. From the Fig. C.2, it can be observed that starting from the 10th iteration, each iteration has only a small change in order to satisfy the iteration stopping condition.

Figure C.1: The results of 4 key iterations of the 21 iterations of EM algorithm, when the MultiCam is used and the LED module is in the middle.

When the LED module is in the corner, the iterations using the MultiCam are shown in Fig. C.3. In Fig. 6.34, the low resolution of Multicam causes the two Gaussian

Figure C.2: The absolute variation between consecutive iterations of the log-likelihood, when the MultiCam is used and the LED module is in the middle.

distributions to overlap. After 24 iterations, the final result in Fig. C.3(d) also shows that the two Gaussian models overlap when terminating the iterations. Meanwhile, this demonstrates the high precision of the EM algorithm.

Figure C.3: The results of 4 key iterations of the 24 iterations of EM algorithm, when the MultiCam is used and the LED module is in the bottom-left.

Figure C.4: The absolute variation between consecutive iterations of the log-likelihood, when the MultiCam is used and the LED module is in the bottom-left.

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